

D4.2 Report on FLIARA Community of Practice Networking events

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
COP	Community of Practice
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
LAG	Local Action Group
SAP	Strategic Action Plan (D4.1)
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
WP	Work Package
MER	Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting

Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

INTRODUCTION

The FLIARA (Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas) project was devised against the backdrop of profound challenges and opportunities shaping rural Europe: demographic decline, uneven access to services, gender gaps in employment and leadership, and the pressing need for sustainable transitions in farming and rural economies. European strategies such as the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy highlighted the importance of innovation, resilience and inclusion, yet the experience of women leading rural and agricultural innovation often remained fragmented, under-recognised and structurally constrained. Within this wider landscape, FLIARA sought to support a more inclusive and sustainable rural innovation ecosystem for innovative women by connecting evidence, policy, community practices and lived experience. In this context, WP4, alongside all FLIARA WPs, played a key role in delivering the multi-actor approach for the FLIARA project, by bringing women innovators into dialogue with AKIS and CAP Network actors, researchers, policy and decision-makers and creating the conditions for meaningful knowledge exchange across research, policy and practice.

WP4's mandate, as defined in the Grant Agreement and further developed in the Strategic Action Plan, was to create a collaborative space where FLIARA Ambassadors, innovative women, Consortium partners and other rural stakeholders could work together, share knowledge and build relationships that supported women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. Rather than operating as a standalone work package, WP4 functioned as a shared project infrastructure, enabling different strands of research, policy exploration, visibility work and ethical attention to meet in practice. The Community of Practice (CoP) was the primary mechanism through which this infrastructure took shape. According to the Grant Agreement, WP4 was tasked with creating a European-wide Community of Practice Network, organising macro-regional networking and learning events and contributing to the foundations of the FLIARA Toolkit so that project knowledge could circulate beyond the events themselves.

The Community of Practice centred on a series of events but functioned as a methodology that invited partners and Ambassadors into a process of shared inquiry. At the centre of the FLIARA CoP stood the Ambassadors, women leading innovative practices in agriculture and rural areas whose insights and experiences guided the learning and focus of each gathering. The CoP was designed to facilitate policy dialogue and participatory scenario development, enable knowledge exchange between innovators, researchers, policymakers and rural actors, and support the development of skills and capacities needed for gender-responsive, inclusive, sustainable rural innovation, while also strengthening the visibility and recognition of women innovators within broader rural ecosystems. Through transnational encounters, innovation journey learning, policy workshops, skills-building sessions, and reflective dialogue, the CoP created a multi-actor setting where diverse forms of knowledge could circulate and interact. This enabled women's innovation journeys, research findings and policy questions to inform and reshape one another and supported a deeper understanding of

the contexts in which rural and agricultural innovation emerged. In this way, the CoP reflected the project's broader commitment to relational learning, mutual support, and cross-country collaboration.

The structure of the CoP reflected this orientation. Four macro-regional FLIARA CoP Networking Events were held in Ireland, Slovenia, Italy and Sweden, offering opportunities for regional exchange, engagement with local and EU actors and contextualised learning across diverse rural settings. Four online CoP sessions complemented these gatherings by providing accessible formats for knowledge sharing, thematic focus and continuity across geographical distances. The macro-regional events fulfilled the GA requirement to organise geographically distributed networking and learning workshops, while the online sessions ensured continuity and enabled broader participation across the project. As required by the GA's multi-actor model, the CoP brought together actors across research, policy, practice and rural communities, namely FLIARA Ambassadors and women innovators, AKIS representatives, CAP Network actors, policymakers, researchers and practitioners, and this diversity actively shaped the exchanges, scenario work and policy discussions throughout the events. Over the course of the project, Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting (MER) cycles shaped the adaptive development of each gathering, guiding decisions around translation, facilitation, agenda design and participation support. These iterative adjustments ensured that the process remained attentive to accessibility, care and the diverse needs of the CoP members.

This deliverable documents the design, implementation and outcomes of the Community of Practice within FLIARA. It provides an overview of the activities hosted under WP4, outlines the methodological approach that guided their development and reflects on the outcomes that emerged for FLIARA Ambassadors, partners and the project. The report also presents the connections between the CoP and other work packages, illustrating how WP4 supported the broader project architecture through shared learning, collaborative reflection and ongoing exchange. Taken together, this deliverable shows how WP4 carried out the multi-actor, collaborative and cross-WP functions assigned to it in the GA and reinforced in the SAP, supporting coherence between WP1–WP5 while strengthening the community of practice methodological approach at the heart of FLIARA's aims for inclusive and sustainable rural innovation ecosystems. In doing so, the CoP upheld the core objective of FLIARA: to support women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas and contribute to more inclusive, resilient and sustainable rural futures.

OVERVIEW AND ROADMAP FOR THE FLIARA COP

PURPOSE AND VISION OF THE FLIARA COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

In line with current definitions, a Community of Practice (CoP) is understood in FLIARA as a group of people who share a concern, challenge, or interest (a practice) and who deepen their knowledge and practice through ongoing interaction (Brightman et al., 2021). In the context of the Grant Agreement, the FLIARA CoP was conceived as a transnational space bringing together innovative women in agriculture and rural areas to share experiences, strengthen capacities, engage with policy makers, and contribute directly to FLIARA's work on women-led rural innovation. As highlighted in the EU Communities of Practice Playbook, effective Communities of Practice are learning-oriented spaces built around sustained interaction, trust and differentiated forms of participation, enabling participants to contribute in diverse ways over time rather than through uniform modes of engagement (European Commission, 2023).

Figure 1 Three Core Dimensions of a CoP

Within WP4, the Community of Practice functioned as a structured yet flexible space for exchange, where women innovators and other relevant stakeholders could collectively explore enabling and constraining conditions for innovation across rural contexts. Rather than a stand-alone activity, the CoP operated as an ongoing process through which Ambassadors, innovators and participants articulated how women-led innovation takes shape in specific local and national settings, while strengthening the visibility of their work through shared dialogue and interaction.

The D4.1 Strategic Action Plan set out a Road map for the implementation of the FLIARA CoP, specifying the participatory and multi-country character of the CoP and by emphasising an inclusive, intersectional, and context-sensitive approach. It underlined the importance of ensuring equitable participation across countries, languages, and

professional backgrounds and of using facilitation methods that enabled all Ambassadors to contribute. In this way, the CoP was positioned as a core mechanism within WP4 for gathering practice-based insights, informing the development of WP4 outputs (including the FLIARA Toolkit), and creating a structured avenue for women innovators to engage with the project and its results, as well as with one another and other relevant stakeholders.

Figure 2 FLIARA CoP Structure

THE FLIARA COP AND THE ROLE OF AMBASSADORS

Within WP4, the Community of Practice was organised to support different modes and intensities of participation, recognising that sustained learning and collaboration in a transnational setting depend on complementary roles and forms of engagement. Grounding the CoP is the full FLIARA Consortium, responsible for designing, facilitating, and supporting the CoP across the project's three-year duration. The FLIARA Ambassadors occupied a central role as women innovators who actively shaped the CoP by sharing their innovation journeys, engaging in peer exchange and policy discussions, and anchoring collective reflection in concrete local and national contexts. Their contributions were complemented by the involvement of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) and other relevant actors from the rural and agricultural innovation ecosystem, including farming and rural development organisations, LEADER Program/ Local Action Groups (LAGs), policy actors, and, where relevant, representatives connected to CAP and AKIS structures. Together, these groups formed the operational CoP, as enacted through the networking events and associated activities, in line with the SAP's concentric structure, enabling a transnational exchange space in which women innovators,

practitioners, researchers and institutional stakeholders could contribute at varying levels of intensity.

The FLIARA Ambassadors were selected from among the 200 innovative women engaged during WP3, with two women per country invited to participate in the Community of Practice. Their identification and invitation were carried out as part of WP3, in line with the process set out in the Grant Agreement and detailed in deliverable D3.1 - Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection and completed prior to the development of the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1). Each Ambassador had already established a working relationship with the responsible national partner during WP3, which provided continuity and a foundation of trust as they moved into their roles within the CoP. Building on this existing engagement, Ambassadors became central actors in the Community of Practice, contributing their experiences, perspectives and practices to the collective learning, exchange and visibility activities developed under WP4.

Within the CoP, Ambassadors played a sustained and active role throughout both in-person and online activities, bringing their innovation journeys into collective discussion and grounding exchange in the structural conditions shaping women-led innovation in diverse contexts. Through this engagement, they generated practice-based insights that informed WP4 outputs and contributed to the project's policy-oriented work. Their participation was supported through dedicated measures, including the Buddy System, inclusive facilitation and language and accessibility support, enabling confident and meaningful engagement within the transnational CoP environment.

THE COP AS A FLEXIBLE AND ADAPTIVE COMMUNITY

As a living document, the Strategic Action Plan was designed to accommodate learning and adjustment over time, enabling the FLIARA CoP to introduce new measures as needs emerged during implementation. In line with the flexible design of the CoP, procedures were in place to accommodate changes in availability and levels of engagement among Ambassadors over the course of the project. This included situations where an Ambassador became unavailable partway through the CoP process. Together with the University of Galway and the relevant national partner, WP4 initiated a replacement procedure to ensure the continuity of representation. This process was successfully completed, resulting in the selection of a new, available, and motivated Ambassador who was able to join the final CoP event. In another case, where an Ambassador's professional commitments prevented participation in in-person events, alternative forms of engagement were activated, including participation in online meetings, allowing her to remain connected to the CoP and contribute to discussions despite limited availability for travel.

As the process evolved measures were put in place to support further participation if Ambassadors and partners had resources. In addition to responding to unforeseen constraints, WP4 introduced an important improvement in relation to Ambassador participation in the international networking events. The original plan, based on budget allocations, foresaw that each Ambassador had the support to attend one in-person CoP

event outside their country. Early in the process, however, a WP4-led discussion with partners allowed partners to review their budget to support Ambassadors to attend more than one in-person event. Depending on budget availability and logistical feasibility, all Ambassadors were invited to attend remaining CoP events. This adaptive measure significantly increased participation: the fourth CoP networking event in Sweden was attended by ten Ambassadors (half of the full cohort), compared to the six originally planned.

A further activity that complemented the FLIARA CoP was the FLIARA Final Conference held in Brussels. Ambassadors were invited to join this event, and several participated, contributing to panel sessions, networking activities, and stakeholder discussions. Their involvement in the Final Conference reinforced the bonds and networks established during the CoP events and supported the project’s objectives by providing additional visibility for women innovators and by creating another moment of exchange within the broader FLIARA Community of Practice.

Figure 3 FLIARA Roadmap as designed in the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1)

COLLABORATIVE TASK DESIGN AND ITERATIVE PREPARATION PROCESSES

Membership in the FLIARA Community of Practice implied shared learning and exchange with the aim of strengthening collective understanding, competence and co-created outputs. In line with the Strategic Action Plan, task-related sessions implemented during the CoP were therefore designed not only to fulfil the requirements of the Grant Agreement, but also to function as learning-oriented spaces for collaboration, reflection and knowledge exchange among diverse actors.

This approach was an integral part of the FLIARA Community of Practice roadmap and was operationalised through a six-step preparation and reflection cycle applied before and after each in-person Community of Practice event. Task leaders were required to situate their sessions within the wider objectives of the project, prepare content using a common Task Content Builder template, and reflect systematically on each session using a Task Reflection template. These reflections were complemented by feedback from Ambassadors and other participants and were used to inform the design, content and facilitation of subsequent sessions.

The six-step cycle ensured that task sessions evolved iteratively across the CoP sequence, responding to participants' needs while maintaining coherence across work packages. It supported collaborative problem-solving, skill and information exchange, evaluation of emerging insights, and identification of gaps or opportunities requiring further attention. This process also helped to ensure transparency of purpose, clarity of roles, accessible language, and facilitation methods adapted to a multi-actor setting, in line with guidance highlighted in the EU Communities of Practice Playbook and other reference toolkits made available to partners.

By embedding preparation, reflection and adaptation directly into the organisation of task sessions, the FLIARA CoP enabled meaningful participation across different roles and levels of engagement. This approach strengthened the quality and relevance of the work carried out during CoP events and supported the co-creation of outputs across WP4, WP5 and WP6, while remaining responsive to the evolving dynamics of the Community of Practice. Ethical governance and Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting are addressed in dedicated sections later in this report, reflecting their role as ongoing practices throughout CoP implementation.

STAKEHOLDER SELECTION METHODOLOGY

The Grant Agreement established that the FLIARA CoP would apply a multi-actor methodology, bringing together women innovators, researchers, policy actors, and rural development stakeholders to ensure that knowledge flowed horizontally rather than hierarchically. This requirement reflects a relational understanding of multi-actor spaces, in which collective learning and insight emerge through collaboration between actors holding different forms of situated knowledge, rather than through hierarchies based solely on institutional authority. As feminist scholar Donna Haraway (1988) reminds us, “knowledge is always partial, embodied, and made in relation” - a principle that aligns with the CoP's ambition to centre women's lived experiences within wider governance conversations.

Building on this, the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1) translated the GA objectives into a concrete stakeholder-selection strategy. It specified that each FLIARA CoP event should bring together:

- FLIARA Ambassadors and additional innovative women from the host country.
- Local, regional, and national policymakers connected to rural development, gender equality, and agricultural innovation.

- Representatives of LAGs, LEADER structures, and AKIS-type intermediaries.
- Civil society actors, rural organisations, and relevant networks.
- Consortium members involved in workshop design and facilitation.

CO-CREATED SELECTION PROCESS BETWEEN ECOLISE, CE, AND GALWAY

Stakeholder selection was implemented as a collaborative effort led by ECOLISE, Consulta Europa (CE), and the University of Galway, working closely with all national partners. The process combined several layers of knowledge:

1. **WP3 practice-based insights**

National partners, having conducted 200 interviews, held detailed contextual knowledge of local actors, networks, and governance structures. This made them central to identifying which stakeholders were relevant, legitimate, and trusted within each local context.

2. **Task-level requirements**

All three workshops delivered during the in-person FLIARA CoP Networking events required the presence of institutional actors able to contribute meaningfully to discussions on public policies, funding structures, and legal frameworks. This meant that each stakeholder list had to include those:

- a. managing LEADER programmes,
- b. working in agricultural or rural development ministries/agencies,
- c. engaging in gender equality initiatives,
- d. representing civic organisations relevant to local innovation ecosystems.

3. **Transnational and cross-disciplinary balance**

The SAP emphasised equitable participation across sectors, languages, and professional backgrounds. The stakeholder lists were therefore co-developed to ensure mixed groups at tables, avoiding the overrepresentation of policymakers or researchers.

4. **Co-creation and consensus-building**

ECOLISE coordinated iterative rounds of list-building: the first draft by host partners, the second refined with CE and Galway to ensure compliance with multi-actor principles, and the final validated jointly before invitations were issued. This collaborative practice, combining logistical, contextual, and methodological expertise, also strengthened internal cohesion within the consortium, making stakeholder selection itself a CoP-building exercise.

ROLE OF INNOVATIVE WOMEN IN HOST COUNTRIES

In every country, the host partners received strong interest from innovative women beyond the Ambassadors. Many expressed a wish to participate once the event agendas became public and invited them into meaningful exchange spaces. The consortium prioritised their inclusion in line with the GA's commitment to women-led innovation, ensuring that local innovators were present in workshops, field visits, and plenaries. In Italy, this resulted in T4.3 being facilitated bilingually; in Slovenia and Sweden, it created deeper ties between Ambassadors and local women leading sustainability, food, or community projects and it expanded the core of the CoP.

ENGAGEMENT OF POLICYMAKERS AND INSTITUTIONAL ACTORS

The stakeholder selection process successfully brought high-level and nationally relevant actors into the CoP sequence. Across the four in-person events, the invited lists resulted in consistent participation from:

- Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) who delivered speeches during the events, signalling the recognition of women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas as a topic relevant at European level.
- High-level European Commission participation, including a keynote intervention by the Commissioner for Environment, Water Resilience and a Competitive Circular Economy, alongside representatives of the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, who contributed to discussions on rural futures, innovation ecosystems, and funding.
- National institutional actors, including:
 - Ministries of Agriculture,
 - National Rural Networks,
 - Gender equality agencies,
 - Local government representatives.

These actors not only attended but also remained engaged beyond their initial participation. Several sought follow-up conversations with national partners (e.g., in Ireland, the Netherlands, etc.), invited Ambassadors to national-level events, or requested access to FLIARA findings for policy development. This demonstrated the effectiveness of the multi-actor selection strategy and its alignment with the feminist principle that “women’s knowledge becomes political when institutions listen”.

OUTCOMES OF THE STAKEHOLDER SELECTION METHODOLOGY

The selection approach achieved several objectives:

- Ensured representation of all key categories foreseen in the GA and SAP.
- Enabled meaningful exchanges between Ambassadors, rural innovation and development actors, and policymakers.
- Contributed to policy impact, as institutional representatives showed continued engagement.

- Strengthened the internal CoP, because the collaborative method of building invitation lists became a practice of internal multi-actor learning itself.
- Increased visibility and legitimacy of FLIARA's messages, especially when MEPs, EU officials, and national representatives participated CoP activities.
- Enabled local-to-EU knowledge flows and vice versa, grounding discussions in lived practice rather than abstract policy language.

Overall, the stakeholder selection process became a substantive component of how the CoP operated, shaping both its methodological coherence and its political relevance. It gave concrete expression to the GA's multi-actor vision, operationalised the SAP's participatory commitments, and ensured that the FLIARA CoP became a space where the FLIARA Ambassadors and women innovators, policymakers at local, regional, national and EU levels, LEADER and LAG representatives, AKIS-related intermediaries, rural development organisations, civil-society and community actors, and researchers could meet as co-producers of sustainable rural futures.

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE ENGAGEMENT AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES

Figure 4 Sequence of FLIARA CoP in person and online events

MACRO-REGIONAL IN-PERSON COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE NETWORKING EVENTS

At the core of the FLIARA Community of Practice were the four macro-regional networking events, which took place in Galway, Ireland (1–2 July 2024), Ljubljana, Slovenia (25–26 September 2024), Rende, Italy (29–30 January 2025) and Växjö, Sweden (14–15 May 2025). The events were hosted by the partners Galway University, Ljubljana University (LU), University of Calabria (UNICAL) and Linnaeus University (LNU).

Figure 5 Map of the FLIARA four CoP Macro-regional Networking Events

The implementation of the FLIARA Community of Practice followed the sequencing and participatory principles established in the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1), through which the transnational dimension of WP4 was realised via a shared Community of Practice. This process began with the first online FLIARA CoP event on 30 May 2024, a private internal meeting for Ambassadors and the Consortium. The kick-off session introduced the CoP structure, opened the shared online spaces, and provided the first opportunity for Ambassadors to meet one another across countries, enabling early connection-building and laying the foundation for the shared methodology applied throughout the FLIARA CoP implementation. Shortly after, the first in-person FLIARA CoP Networking Event in Galway (1–2 July, 2024) initiated the face-to-face learning journey together with EU- and national-level policy makers, combining innovation journey sharing, policy workshops

and collective reflection on women-led innovation, in line with WP4's emphasis on participatory, practice-based learning.

On 25-26 September, the 2nd FLIARA CoP Networking (in person) event in Ljubljana deepened the thematic focus on networks, sustainability practices, and community-based innovation. Building on the foundations laid in Galway, the Ljubljana event shifted the emphasis of the CoP toward more place-based and community-embedded forms of exchange, bringing together Ambassadors, innovative women from Slovenia, consortium partners, and relevant stakeholders and including a field visit to Ambassadors and community entrepreneurs. Shortly afterward, the 2nd FLIARA Online CoP Event on 14 November 2024 was held as a public event, reflecting the SAP's intention to open selected online moments to wider audiences. This session included a highly appreciated cybersecurity training delivered by Irish FLIARA Innovator Aoife Noone, as well as breakout-group exchanges tailored to support Ambassadors preparing for upcoming events. The public nature of this session allowed for broader engagement with the FLIARA community and external stakeholders while still maintaining an intimate learning environment for the Ambassadors.

Figure 6 Group photos at each of the four CoP events

The 3rd FLIARA CoP Networking Event in Rende (29-30 January 2025) focused on governance, social innovation, and rural transformation processes. Importantly, one workshop was facilitated in Italian, enabling additional local innovative women to participate and ensuring that language barriers did not limit the inclusion of local perspectives. On 30 April 2025, the 3rd Online CoP Event, also a public session, explored the theme "Bridging Private and Public Funding for Women Innovators in

Agriculture and Rural Areas.” This event connected Ambassadors with institutional and financial actors and served as a preparatory moment before the final in-person meeting. Participation from Ambassadors, innovative women, and external stakeholders strengthened the visibility and policy-relevance objectives of the FLIARA CoP.

The 4th FLIARA CoP Networking in-person event in Växjö (14-15 May 2025) concluded the in-person sequence. With the highest number of Ambassadors attending (10), this event explored future scenarios, rural resilience, and collective visioning, integrating lessons from earlier gatherings. The CoP process closed with the 4th Online CoP Event on 17 November 2025, a private closing session dedicated to reflection, meaning-making, celebration, and appreciation. This final meeting provided space for Ambassadors and the Consortium to review the full CoP journey, highlight its transformative elements, and articulate key messages to feed into FLIARA’s concluding outputs. Taken together, the four in-person and four online events formed a coherent, adaptive, and ethically grounded FLIARA CoP process that delivered on, and in several respects exceeded, the participatory vision set out in the GA and SAP.

The online CoP events played a crucial role in making the FLIARA Community of Practice both continuous and accessible. They created more accessible entry points for Ambassadors who faced time, care, financial, or mobility constraints, allowing them to stay connected to the process even when travel was not possible. Scheduled strategically between in-person gatherings, the online sessions functioned as preparatory and debriefing spaces where expectations could be clarified, experiences shared, and emerging findings translated across countries. Public-facing online events extended this dynamic further by opening CoP discussions on funding, governance, and women’s innovation to a wider audience, while keeping Ambassadors at the centre. Taken together, the online events ensured that participation in the CoP was not limited to those able to attend physical meetings but could be sustained over time and across diverse personal and structural circumstances. See the Annexes for the full detailed event reports for each of the four FLIARA CoP in-person networking events.

From the beginning, the FLIARA Community of Practice was conceived not as a series of static events, but as a living infrastructure, a transnational space that would grow, and refine itself through experience, while maintaining the Ambassadors at the centre of women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas as its domain. This vision placed collaboration and co-creation, ethical care, monitoring, evaluation, and reporting at the heart of the process, not as administrative obligations, but as the shared infrastructure that enabled the FLIARA CoP to evolve as a community of practice, capable of adapting over time and strengthening its capacity to support women-led rural innovation.

With each gathering, online or in person, the CoP learned something new about what women innovators needed to feel safe, visible, and heard; about how cross-sector conversations could flow more equitably; and about how the project team could refine methods to better support the collaborative work at the centre of WP4. The iterative cycle of MER created a rhythm: implement, observe, reflect, adapt. In practice, this rhythm

translated into concrete and meaningful improvements across the four in-person CoP events.

The following sequence of Community of Practice events illustrates how learning, reflection and adaptation accumulated across the FLIARA CoP process, drawing on feedback and experience from Ambassadors, consortium partners, facilitators and participating stakeholders, and feeding into the continuous refinement of formats, engagement methods and support measures, as described in the Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting approach for the CoP set out in this report.

FROM GALWAY TO LJUBLJANA: DEEPENING CONNECTION AND CONTEXT

The first CoP in Galway was a milestone, an energising beginning that showed the potential of bringing Ambassadors, innovators, policymakers, LAG representatives and researchers together in one room. Yet the monitoring and feedback mechanisms immediately revealed areas where the living CoP could grow. Participants asked for more time to speak to one another, more opportunity to see rural realities first-hand, and materials that were easier to navigate across languages.

Figure 7 Galway CoP: Irish MEP Maria Walsh (IE), Innovators (IE), Ambassador Anja Frey (DE), Minister of State at the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine Pippa Hackett (IE), Ambassador Ursula Kelly (IE), FLIARA SAB member Steve Dolan, Ambassador Blátnaid Gallagher (IE), FLIARA Project Coordinator Maura Farrell and Project Manager Louise Weir (Galway University), and Ambassador Annette Harberink (NL)

The move from CoP 1 (Galway) to CoP 2 (Ljubljana) therefore became the first major test of the MER cycle. The Slovenian team, together with ECOLISE and the University of Galway team, rebalanced the programme to open more space for networking, reducing the intensity and repetition that had shaped the inaugural event. They introduced a full-day field visit, an addition not foreseen in the SAP, but fully aligned with the CoP's commitment to grounding discussions in lived experience. Visual materials were expanded, exhibitions made bilingual, and poster presentations placed prominently to strengthen recognition of all 20 Ambassadors. Workshop facilitation instructions were refined, and table compositions became more intentional, ensuring diversity and equitable participation. Even the Ambassador Innovation Journey was redesigned, held in a more inviting and participatory space that allowed Ambassadors to share their stories with greater ease.

These adjustments illustrate how MER shaped practice by listening closely to participants, absorbing their insights, and immediately translating these into better design and stronger inclusion.

Figure 8 Field trip during the 2nd CoP networking event in Slovenia

FROM LJUBLJANA TO RENDE: TRUST-BUILDING AND DEEPER ENGAGEMENT

If the shift in the CoP from Galway to Ljubljana focused on structure and flow, the transition made in the CoP from Ljubljana to Rende centred on relationships. MER feedback highlighted the importance of creating protected spaces within the CoP that

complemented public-facing sessions, enabling Ambassadors to spend more time together and engage in facilitated exchanges that supported openness, trust-building and peer learning alongside expert discussion.

UNICAL responded by introducing a dedicated Ambassador-only networking activity, the “Networking Aperitif”, which became one of the most appreciated elements of the event. WP6 visibility work was reimagined as well: interview questions were sent in advance, a dedicated recording room was created, and micro-slots during breaks allowed for a more respectful and less intrusive process.

Multilingual support was significantly strengthened, including Italian-language parallel facilitation, reflecting the linguistic diversity of the participants and ensuring equitable access to participation. The Ambassador Journey was given more time and adapted to Italian cultural and social rhythms, allowing narratives to unfold more naturally and connecting the political meaning of women’s innovation to the local landscape.

Figure 9 Part of the FLIARA Ambassadors during the CoP event in Italy

These refinements were not merely technical improvements; they represented a shift in the emotional and relational architecture of the CoP. The Italian event revealed how a well-monitored and well-evaluated process could foster trust, solidarity, and interdependence: the foundations of any resilient community.

FROM RENDE TO VÄXJÖ: ALIGNMENT, STRUCTURE, AND POLITICAL DEPTH

By the time the CoP travelled to Växjö, monitoring and evaluation had created a finely tuned understanding of what made the CoP work. Building on accumulated learning, the Swedish partners delivered a logistically smooth and politically substantive CoP in the sequence.

MER from Rende highlighted the need for clearer logistical guidance during field visits, more structured pacing, accessible facilities, and predictable breaks. The Swedish agenda responded with meticulous planning and clear participant communication. Acoustic and spatial challenges noted in previous events were resolved through improved room arrangements, enabling more focused workshop exchanges.

Parallel workshops were also more structured, with balanced table composition and facilitation adapted to both Swedish and international participants. Ambassadors had repeatedly expressed a desire for deeper engagement with gender policy, and Växjö delivered: keynotes and discussions directly addressed gender norms, labour, childcare policy, and the structural conditions of women's innovation within a Nordic context.

Figure 10 Linktree structure and materials for the 4th FLIARA CoP Networking Event (CE)

The introduction of an Ambassador-exclusive fika (coffee time) created a resonant moment of mutual trust building and horizontal exchange, strengthening cross-national relationships that had grown steadily since Galway. Communication flows were tightened, with better visibility of Linktree materials, posters, and summaries.

By the end of the fourth CoP, the MER cycle had reached a level of maturity reflected in exceptionally high participant satisfaction scores. More importantly, it had supported the emergence of a community whose practices and relationships had evolved through shared reflection and iterative learning across the CoP process.

Taken together, the progression from Galway to Växjö demonstrates how the FLIARA Community of Practice evolved through iterative learning, monitoring and adaptation, with each event informing refinements in design, facilitation and support. While this section focuses on how learning accumulated across the CoP process, the Outcomes and Impact of the FLIARA Community of Practice section synthesises what this learning enabled in terms of strengthened networks, empowerment, visibility and policy relevance.

ONLINE COP NETWORKING EVENTS AND SPACES

While the Grant Agreement only foresaw the organisation of four in-person FLIARA CoP networking events in each macro-region, the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1) expanded this structure to include a series of online engagements, recognising their value for continuity, accessibility, and sustained interaction within the Community of Practice. To complement the online CoP events operationalised through the D4.1 Strategic Action Plan, the Consortium also developed an online interaction space designed to extend participation, sustain exchanges between events, and support the wider engagement of various stakeholders with the Community of Practice.

Figure 11 FLIARA COP LinkedIn Group

In line with the GA's commitment to multi-actor participation and the SAP's emphasis on continuous engagement, the Consortium established a dedicated FLIARA CoP LinkedIn group as an online space for interaction, knowledge sharing, and good-practice exchange. The decision to opt for a LinkedIn group reflected a Consortium decision and the project's aim to facilitate ample, continuous stakeholder engagement beyond those able to attend in-person or online events. Engagement in the group remained limited, as multiple other opportunities for direct interaction were consistently available through the CoP workshops and events, as well as other FLIARA activities and events. The group was monitored and facilitated by ECOLISE and CE, with contributions from all Consortium partners. In accordance with contractual requirements and GDPR provisions, the group was closed at the end of the project.

The SAP anticipated five online events; in practice, four were implemented. This decision followed a careful assessment of Ambassador needs and the evolving dynamics of the CoP: rather than meeting a numerical target, the Consortium prioritised purpose-driven encounters that supported preparation, reflection, and ongoing connection. In addition to the four online sessions, the consortium organised a public webinar on funding opportunities and invited Ambassadors to the Final Conference, ensuring multiple complementary spaces for exchange. Throughout, the underlying logic remained consistent with WP4's participatory ethos to enhance interaction opportunities for the

CoP as a living community, and especially to provide meaningful, accessible touchpoints for the Ambassadors.

1st Online CoP Event – Kick-off (30 May 2024)

The first online CoP event marked the formal beginning of the FLIARA Community of Practice. Held on 30 May 2024, it gathered 35 participants (15 Ambassadors and 20 consortium members), providing the first shared space for cross-country introductions, alignment of expectations, and the launch of the FLIARA StoryMap, an early visibility tool showcasing the 20 Ambassadors' innovation journeys.

Figure 12 Screenshot of the 1st FLIARA Online CoP Event

Breakout-room discussions explored the question “How can the CoP benefit you and your work?”, revealing early convergences across countries: the need for collective learning, visibility, inspiration, and a sense of community among women innovating in isolated or male-dominated rural environments.

Monitoring and evaluation highlighted the value of this first encounter but also identified pivotal technical and organisational adjustments: clearer instructions for breakout rooms, slower facilitation pace to support non-native speakers, and more time for small-group interaction. Notably, it was during this event that the Consortium identified the need for strengthened language accessibility and created the Buddy System to provide continuous personal support for Ambassadors throughout the entire CoP process.

The event also marked the launch of the dedicated LinkedIn CoP space, initially conceived as a closed group, but following monitoring and evaluation, was later opened to broader stakeholders to increase engagement and visibility.

2nd Online CoP Event: Reflection, Support, and Cybersecurity (14 November 2024)

The second online event took place mid-way through the sequence of in-person CoPs, at a critical moment when Ambassadors were processing their experiences from Galway and Ljubljana and preparing for the events to come. The session was intentionally small and intimate: 11 Ambassadors, one innovative woman (Aoife Noone), and 14 consortium members.

The focus on digital security and online safety reflected needs identified during WP3 interviews with women innovators, as well as concerns raised during discussions at the first Community of Practice events regarding visibility, online exposure and safe participation in transnational networks. Its design responded directly to feedback from the first CoP and from in-person events. Three elements defined its structure:

- A reflective check-in on experiences to date
- Breakout rooms paired ambassadors who had already travelled with those preparing for Italy and Sweden
- A specialised training input, responding to Ambassador-requested needs, delivered by cybersecurity expert and FLIARA innovative woman Aoife Noone

Figure 13 Screenshot of the 2nd Online FLIARA CoP Event

Monitoring emphasised linguistic accessibility: automatic closed captions were activated; short guides on how to use them were circulated; and Buddies accompanied Ambassadors in breakout rooms to translate or clarify in real time. This measure, evaluated as highly effective, was maintained for subsequent online events.

Feedback highlighted the value of direct peer-to-peer exchange, the reassurance offered by hearing from Ambassadors who had already participated in in-person events, and the strong appreciation for the tailored cybersecurity intervention. Although survey participation was low (4 responses, all consortium members), the Ethics Guardian, who moved across breakout rooms, confirmed high levels of comfort, engagement, and well-being among participants.

3rd Online CoP Event: “Bridging Private and Public Funding for Women Innovators” (30 April 2025)

The third online CoP represented a shift in tone and purpose: it was a public-facing session, intentionally designed to expand the CoP’s reach and connect Ambassadors and innovative women to wider financial and institutional actors. The event explored funding gaps, opportunities, and inequalities affecting women-led rural and agricultural innovations, drawing from both project evidence and external expertise. The focus on access to finance and funding pathways reflected persistent barriers identified during WP3 research, as well as recurring issues raised by Ambassadors during CoP workshops and peer exchanges, particularly regarding unequal access to capital, information asymmetries, and the challenges of navigating public and private funding instruments in rural contexts.

Figure 14 Poster for the 3rd FLIARA Online CoP Event

The session brought together a diverse range of funding and support actors, including the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre presenting EU-level funding pathways, the EU CAP Network outlining opportunities through EIP-AGRI and rural

development cooperation instruments, AskGrant offering insights into navigating public and private fundraising landscapes, and TERINOV showcasing incubation-based support and entrepreneurial financing routes for women-led rural innovation.

Building on MER findings from previous online events, the structure featured:

- A clear, visually guided agenda shared in advance
- A strong moderation sequence that linked FLIARA data to external funding realities
- Breakout discussions tailored to identify barriers and possibilities in national contexts

The event strengthened FLIARA's policy learning dimension: participants repeatedly emphasised structural challenges such as the gendered distribution of risk in rural enterprise, underrepresentation in rural investment ecosystems, and the need for hybridised funding models. These inputs contributed to the broader policy learning process of the project, including discussions and analytical work carried out under WP5 and within the Gender Benchmarking framework.

Monitoring showed strong appreciation for the practical relevance of the topic, and clear interest in follow-up sessions. This was also a means for the Consortium to offer the Ambassadors, and the rest of the FLIARA CoP, access to relevant knowledge regarding public and private funding in the EU.

4th Online CoP Event: Closing Session (17 November 2025)

Figure 15 Screenshot of the 4th FLIARA Online CoP event

The final online event was designed as a private, reflective, and celebratory closing session, bringing together Ambassadors and the Consortium after the completion of all in-person FLIARA CoPs. Rather than introducing new content, the event emphasised:

- Collective reflection on the two-year CoP journey

- Meaning-making across countries, roles, and experiences
- Identifying personal and collective transformation
- Sharing messages for future generations of women innovators
- Celebrating the bonds, solidarities, and collaborations that emerged

The closing session thus completed the full CoP cycle. Ambassadors reflected openly on how participation had shaped their leadership, expanded their networks, and strengthened their confidence. Feedback emphasised the value of having protected, trust-based space at the end of the process, mirroring the iterative learning the CoP had applied at every step.

A warm, inclusive atmosphere characterised the session, with participants staying actively engaged throughout. The depth of connection and mutual recognition within the group was clearly visible, underscoring the symbolic and emotional significance of closing the CoP in an online space accessible to all Ambassadors, regardless of their ability to travel.

Overall Contribution of Online Events to WP4

Taken together, the four online CoP events became a central component of WP4's success. They ensured continuity between in-person events, created accessible touchpoints for preparation and debriefing, expanded the visibility of the CoP to external audiences, and provided thematic depth on issues, such as cybersecurity and funding, that Ambassadors themselves identified as crucial. The MER practices applied throughout enabled the online environment to function as a genuinely participatory extension of the in-person CoPs, reinforcing the FLIARA CoP as a community that evolves with its members.

ETHICS AND DATA MANAGEMENT

Ethical principles guided the design and implementation of all FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) activities, in full compliance with Article 14 of the Grant Agreement and the procedures established in Deliverable D4.1 Strategic Action Plan (SAP), grounded on the project's Data Management Plan (D7.1, D7.2). Beyond formal compliance, the Consortium adopted an ethics-in-practice approach, ensuring that inclusion, well-being, and the autonomy of participants, particularly the FLIARA Ambassadors, remained at the centre of all CoP processes. All additional details related to ethical approaches within the FLIARA project activities can be found in Deliverable D8.1, where adopted measures ensuring compliance with ethical and fundamental rights and standards are highlighted.

ETHICAL GOVERNANCE AND OVERSIGHT

Ethical oversight was coordinated by the University of Galway, as WP8 Lead, together with ECOLISE as WP4 Lead. The role of FLIARA Ethics guardian was held by professor Milada Šťastná, representing Consortium partner Mendel University in Brno. She monitored the ethical environment across all CoP activities. Acting as a neutral observer and point of contact, the Ethics guardian participated in each in-person event, gathered

feedback, and produced an ethics summary report after every CoP (as per the SAP Monitoring and Evaluation planning). These reports were discussed by ECOLISE and the University of Galway and informed adjustments to subsequent events.

The Ethics guardian's role complemented the responsibility of all partners to uphold ethical standards in their respective tasks. This collaborative model ensured that attention to well-being and inclusivity was embedded across the Consortium rather than isolated in one role, and covered all activities, from planning to implementation and evaluation.

IMPLEMENTATION OF IN-PERSON AND ONLINE EVENTS

For all in-person events (Galway, Ljubljana, Rende, Växjö), ethical practice focused on informed participation, care, and accessibility. The input and collaboration of the host partners (Galway University, Ljubljana University, Calabria University and Linnaeus University) was fundamental in being able to implement correctly the ethics guidelines.

- Before events, participants received clear information sheets and consent forms (prepared by ECOLISE and Consulta Europa with input from Galway and the host partner) covering data use, photography, and recording for communication purposes.
- During events, the Ethics guardian observed interactions, paying attention to speaking time, comfort, and inclusiveness. The agenda always included breaks and informal social moments to reduce fatigue and foster mutual care.
- After events, participants were invited to provide anonymous feedback through digital surveys designed jointly by ECOLISE, Galway, the host institution and the Ethics guardian. Feedback was analysed and integrated into the planning of the next CoP.

For online events, ECOLISE applied the same principles within digital settings: all sessions used GDPR-compliant registration forms, explicit consent for recording, and moderated chat functions to ensure respectful dialogue. The Ethics guardian attended these meetings to monitor atmosphere and follow up individually if wellbeing concerns emerged.

BUDDY SYSTEM TO SUPPORT ETHICAL, INCLUSIVE PARTICIPATION

The Strategic Action Plan (D4.1) articulated a commitment to supporting ethical, inclusive participation within the Community of Practice, while explicitly framing the SAP as a living document open to adaptation as needs emerged during implementation. In this context, more concrete support measures were developed iteratively over the course of the CoP. One such example was the introduction of a Buddy System by the University of Galway team, which operationalised this commitment by creating a clear, person-centred support structure that strengthened confidence, communication and inclusive participation conditions across the CoP.

The need for this system became evident during early coordination with the newly selected Ambassadors, when differing communication needs, confidence levels, and logistical questions highlighted the importance of offering each Ambassador a stable, familiar point of contact. Methodologically, pairing built on pre-existing relationships: Ambassadors were matched with members of the Consortium who had worked within their national context, typically the researcher who had first identified them as innovators, conducted their interviews, and later participated in their selection. This ensured continuity, trust, and contextual understanding from the outset. The Buddy System was implemented for the entire duration of the FLIARA CoP, rather than being linked to specific events, to provide sustained, accessible communication channels and to ensure that Ambassadors felt supported throughout their engagement. It also streamlined communication by giving each Ambassador a clear, trusted first point of contact.

In practice, Buddies contextualised discussions, supported Ambassadors facing language or confidence barriers, and ensured space for quieter participants to express themselves. They also flagged any concerns to the Ethics Guardian, Galway University Team, ECOLISE, or the relevant host partner, enabling timely facilitation adjustments when needed. This ongoing relational work in practice meant regular informal check-ins, collaborative troubleshooting (especially around travel, accessibility, and communication barriers), and active accompaniment during sessions. Overall, the Buddy System became both an important ethical safeguard as well as an effective way to create and strengthen the CoP.

In this way, the Buddy System developed beyond an abstract commitment to inclusion into a concrete ethical practice within the CoP, strengthening Ambassadors' wellbeing, communication and inclusive engagement throughout the FLIARA project.

LANGUAGE AND TRANSLATION CONSIDERATIONS

Figure 16 Italian speaking group during policy workshop at the 3rd FLIARA Networking Event

Given the multilingual nature of the FLIARA Community of Practice and the differing levels of English proficiency among participants, language accessibility emerged as an ethical priority throughout implementation. Already identified in the D4.1 Strategic Action Plan, we significantly expanded these measures during delivery. Together with the University of Galway, the Ethics guardian, Consulta Europa (CE), the local host partner, and the Ambassador Buddies, we introduced collaborative practices to reduce linguistic barriers and address the self-doubt some participants expressed when speaking in a non-native language. Measures included providing translated preparatory materials in advance, ensuring informal translation support during in-person events, and actively facilitating multilingual exchanges in online spaces. In Italy, one workshop was delivered in both English and the local language, with the host partner Calabria University supporting facilitation and the translation of the data collected. This approach broadened access to FLIARA knowledge for innovative women who might otherwise have been excluded and ensured that language was not an obstacle to the innovative women expressing their experiences or contributing meaningfully to the project. Across all events (online and in person), participants were also encouraged to adopt inclusive conversational norms, speaking slowly, allowing pauses, avoiding jargon, and ensuring space for all voices to be heard. These actions went beyond GA commitments and strengthened equitable participation within the CoP.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND GDPR-ALIGNED REGISTRATION PROCESSES

Data management measures applied during the implementation of the FLIARA CoP followed the procedures outlined in the D4.1 Strategic Action Plan (SAP) and the FLIARA Data Management Plan, ensuring full compliance with GDPR and Article 14 of the Grant Agreement. For every in-person and online CoP activity, participation was conditional on completion of a GDPR-compliant registration form that clearly outlined the purpose of data collection, data retention periods, rights of participants, and limits of data use. Registration forms were designed and managed jointly by ECOLISE and Consulta Europa, with input from the University of Galway and the respective host partner to ensure clarity, accessibility, and legal accuracy. Only data strictly necessary for event organisation, communication, and evaluation were collected, and all personal information was stored on secure, access-controlled platforms for the minimum period required by the project's contractual obligations. No personal data were shared beyond the Consortium, and all processing activities were logged in accordance with the SAP's data monitoring requirements.

ADAPTIVE MEASURES SUPPORTING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SAP

In line with the Strategic Action Plan's role as a living document, the implementation of the Community of Practice involved the introduction and refinement of a number of measures responding to emerging needs during the CoP process:

- The Ethics Guardian contributed reflective inputs after each CoP event, in line with the evaluation framework set out in the Strategic Action Plan, supporting continuous reflection, learning and adaptation throughout the CoP process.
- Partner hosts integrated dedicated networking and trust-building activities to support Ambassadors' wellbeing and create informal spaces for connection (e.g. the Ambassadors' Aperitif in Italy, the fika/coffee time in Sweden).
- Field visits were integrated into the CoP programme in Slovenia, Italy and Sweden, responding to Ambassador feedback on the importance of grounding discussions in lived rural realities.
- A digital community (FLIARA CoP LinkedIn group) was established and moderated by the Consortium during the project and will remain active for a further two years after project completion under the coordination of partner CE.

Overall, the Community of Practice provided a concrete space in which the ethical standards and commitments articulated at project level in D8.1, D7.1 and D7.2 were actively implemented and sustained in practice. Through continuous reflection on participation, wellbeing and inclusion, the CoP supported learning environments that were respectful, transparent and safe, ensuring that the visibility and empowerment of women innovators were consistently accompanied by dignity, care and trust.

POLICY WORKSHOPS

Across the four in-person FLIARA Community of Practice events held in Galway, Ireland (July 2024), Ljubljana, Slovenia (September 2024), Rende, Italy (January 2025) and Växjö, Sweden (May 2025), the FLIARA Consortium implemented a coherent and iterative programme of three interconnected policy workshops:

- Policy Focus Groups / Policy Design (Task 4.3)
- Future Foresight / Participatory Scenario Development (Task 5.3)
- Policy Practice Discussions (Task 5.2)

Together, these workshops formed a central element of the methodological architecture defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and further operationalised in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP). They supported the Community of Practice's purpose of enabling multi-actor exchange, advancing gender policy benchmarking, co-producing future-oriented policy insights, and strengthening women innovators' capacity to engage with governance processes.

The image shows a vertical discussion card with a purple header and green question bars. The header contains the FLIARA logo and the text 'Name (if you want)' and 'country'. Below the header, there are two columns: 'Innovation (farming or rural area)' and 'Location: rural village, remote rural areas, rural areas close to city'. The main body of the card contains four green question bars: 'How did you overcome this challenge?', 'Solution for the future?', 'Which regulations needs to change?', and 'What level of policy regulation should change?'. The card has rounded corners and a thin border.

Figure 17 Example of Discussion Card used in the Policy Practice Workshop (T5.2)

The workshops were designed and led by the responsible partners:

- ECOLISE, in collaboration with the University of Galway, for Task 4.3.
- University of Turku and the University of Galway for Task 5.3.
- TU Delft for Task 5.2.

All workshops were implemented collaboratively with the support of the wider FLIARA Consortium, whose contributions included participant preparation, facilitation, note-taking, table moderation, and the integration of accessibility and inclusion measures.

TASK 4.3 - POLICY BENCHMARKING/DESIGN FOCUS GROUP

The first workshop, corresponding to Task 4.3, was designed and led by ECOLISE, working in close collaboration with the University of Galway and with implementation support from all partners. This activity was conceived in the GA as the mechanism for verifying and enriching the assessment of public policies and legal frameworks affecting women-led rural and farm innovations, building on WP1 (in particular T1.4 and D1.5) and WP3 case study findings.

During the Galway pilot, ECOLISE implemented a structured focus group methodology for the first time, using a detailed Focus Group Guide, mixed tables, and carefully sequenced questions to validate national policy information, identify gaps, and understand the lived policy interactions of women innovators. The approach proved robust, with participants emphasising recurrent policy themes- particularly the transversal role of LEADER- which informed the drafting stages of the Benchmarking Initial Report (D4.3). In Ljubljana, the method was refined based on consortium and participant feedback: tables were more intentionally composed, facilitation instructions were strengthened, and an additional question on “policy wishes” was introduced to capture early design-oriented insights.

In the Italian CoP, held in Rende in January 2025 after D4.3 had been submitted, the focus shifted towards policy design. ECOLISE and Galway presented the eleven policy improvement areas identified in D4.3, guiding participants through prioritisation exercises and co-creation of concrete policy wishes that would serve as direct input for the forthcoming WP5 activities. By the time of the Swedish CoP in Växjö (May 2025), T4.3 had evolved into a mature and participatory policy design exercise, again facilitated by ECOLISE and Galway with the assistance of the whole consortium. Here, participants reflected on the relevance of the improvement areas (see figure below) in their national contexts, developed nuanced “policy wishes”, and discussed differences in perceived urgency, for instance, contrasting evaluations of the significance of traditional gender norms between Scandinavian and Southern/Eastern European groups. Across all locations, T4.3 sessions benefitted from the combined facilitation, translation, note-taking, and organisational support of the consortium, resulting in high-quality comparable data that now underpins FLIARA’s gender benchmarking and informs the next steps of WP5.

Areas of future policy improvement to better support women-led innovation?
Specific enabling conditions for women-led farm and rural innovation
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improve access to finance• More tailored supports to different phases and patterns of enterprise development• Better access to networks and peer support• Advance education and skills training for women innovators• Address barriers specific to particular groups of women• Address more specific barriers to women-led farm innovation
The policy support system
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• More innovative policy design• Address barriers in the existing policy support system• Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability
Rural resources, social and cultural conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Address wider rural development issues• Address domestic work distribution and work equity• Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes• Better representation of women in decision making

Figure 18 Areas of policy improvement derived from D4.3 Initial Benchmarking Report

TASK 5.2 - POLICY PRACTICE DISCUSSION WORKSHOP

The third workshop, corresponding to Task 5.2 and was led by TU Delft, where they created a structured policy-practice dialogue aimed at surfacing the challenges, workarounds, and policy changes identified by women innovators and other stakeholders across Europe. In Galway, TU Delft piloted the approach described in the GA and SAP: participants worked collectively to identify key challenges and workarounds, such as funding barriers, family care issues, limited rural landowner, and fragmented information systems(digitalisation), and education, and discussing potential policy responses filled in to a specific form (Figure 17). All facilitators and notetakers received information up forehand. The approach proved effective and was refined for Ljubljana, where TU Delft introduced clearer initial instructions to the workshop, predefined table topics (female, innovation, agriculture, and rural entrepreneurship), and a focus on European and national-level discussion, resulting in more direct and actionable outcomes. The form to describe the problem, solution, and policy fields or levels was adapted and minimised for a clearer process. The organisation of the groups shifted from more focused groups to the most diversity in position and role of expertise as possible. In Slovenia, topics like childcare, inheritance, education, farming/ landownership and community were discussed (see D5.4 annex).

Figure 19 Image from the Policy Practice discussion workshop during the 4th FLIARA CoP Networking Event in Sweden

In Rende, the method continued and refined in small details, to generate relevant insights while also highlighting important regional contrasts, particularly in relation to infrastructure gaps and the persistence of gender norms shaping innovation pathways. The focus in topics discussed focused on funding issues, locality and community, female empowerment, family care, and networking. In Växjö, the workshop design built on the experience accumulated in previous events, enabling more focused exchanges on rural innovation trajectories and policy needs in a Nordic context. The focus in Sweden centred around rural lifestyle, funding, law and family care and community (see D5.4). Across all four events, TU Delft's leadership was complemented by coordinated preparation, facilitation and documentation efforts from the wider Consortium, contributing to methodological coherence across workshops and providing structured inputs for the policy analysis and synthesis work carried out under WP5, and particularly deliverable D5.1 (Policy Booklet and Policy Briefs).

TASK 5.3 - USING FUTURE VISIONS TO BUILD POLICY SUPPORTING WOMEN-LED INNOVATION

The second workshop, corresponding to Task 5.3 and jointly led by the University of Turku and the University of Galway, implemented a participatory futures methodology to co-create scenarios and identify policy measures for women-led innovation. In line with the GA and SAP, this activity drew directly on WP2 findings, specifically the Vision Cards developed from the foresight research. In Galway, the first implementation demonstrated the method's capacity to foster creative, future-oriented discussion, while grounding visions in lived rural contexts. Participants selected Vision Cards they felt women could

meaningfully shape and discussed the measures required to achieve those futures; eight cards were most frequently selected, highlighting themes such as rural image, funding models, and local food systems.

Figure 20 Example of Vision Cards used for the T5.3 workshop

In Ljubljana, the method was expanded by introducing two group formats, Vision Groups for first-time participants and Vision Elaboration Groups for consortium members who had participated in Galway, ensuring both continuity and deeper development of previously generated ideas. Rende further strengthened this structure by introducing Scenario Cards derived from the most selected visions from earlier CoPs (local food, sustainable lifestyles, policymaking). These were used in deliberative back-casting sessions to map pathways from the desired future to the present, integrating Italian participants' strong emphasis on sustainability, territorial identity, and rural livelihoods.

The final iteration in Växjö preserved this two-layered approach but drew new thematic emphases from Swedish participants: "sustainable farming" emerged as the leading vision, shifting the dominant trend observed in earlier countries. Participants engaged intensively without designated note-takers, an intentional methodological choice by UTU and Galway to encourage more spontaneous dialogue, while consortium partners supported room coordination, facilitation, and material preparation. Together, the four iterations of T5.3 generated a rich corpus of future visions, scenario pathways, and policy directions that feed directly into Deliverable D5.2 and the broader WP5 policy design process.

Figure 21 Future Foresight Workshop (T5.3) in Sweden

HOW COP POLICY WORKSHOPS CONTRIBUTED TO FLIARA POLICY OUTPUTS

The policy workshops implemented across the four Community of Practice events constituted a core pathway through which FLIARA translated women innovators' experiences into policy-relevant evidence, proposals and recommendations. Within the Community of Practice, these workshops provided structured, participatory spaces where multi-actor knowledge was generated, tested and refined in direct dialogue with women innovators and governance actors.

- Policy Benchmarking workshops (Task 4.3) generated comparative evidence on gender equality performance and structural barriers within policy, legal and governance frameworks. This work operationalised the gender benchmarking methodology initially defined in WP1 and was documented in Deliverable D4.3 – Benchmarking Initial Report, while also contributing empirical data to Deliverable D5.3 – Gender Benchmarking Report.
- Policy Practice Discussion workshops (Task 5.2) surfaced concrete challenges, workarounds and leverage points at local, national and EU levels, forming the empirical basis for policy briefs and practice-oriented recommendations developed in Deliverable D5.1, Policy Briefs and Deliverable D5.2, Policy Booklet.
- Foresight and Participatory Scenario Development workshops (Task 5.3) used qualitative, multi-actor scenario-building methods to explore future policy contexts and identify options to adapt policy and governance structures to support women-led rural and agricultural innovation. These workshops informed the development of new policy proposals and directly underpin Deliverable D5.2, Participatory Scenario Development Report, which documents the process, tested scenarios and finalised scenario narratives tailored to policy-making contexts.

Together, these workshops produced a coherent, multi-actor and multi-regional body of policy-relevant knowledge, demonstrating how the Community of Practice functioned as a core space for participatory policy development within FLIARA.

THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IN PRACTICE

Across all four CoP events and all three workshops, implementation was a shared effort of the entire FLIARA Consortium and followed the multi-actor approach and stakeholder engagement requirements set out in the GA and the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1 SAP). In line with these commitments, ECOLISE, the University of Galway, TU Delft, the University of Turku, the respective host partners and all consortium partners collaborated in the full cycle of preparation, including the identification and invitation of relevant stakeholders, FLIARA Ambassadors, the national FLIARA women innovators, LAG representatives, civil society actors, researchers, and policy and decision-makers at local, regional, national, and EU levels. Consortium partners worked jointly to ensure participants' meaningful engagement by designing balanced participant lists and carefully distributing stakeholders at tables to guarantee mixed group composition and equitable representation of all categories.

Particular attention was given to positioning FLIARA Ambassadors and women innovation practitioners alongside policymakers and institutional actors, facilitating direct exchanges that fulfilled both the GA's multi-actor requirement and the SAP's emphasis on women-centred knowledge flows. During implementation, Consortium partners contributed through co-design, facilitation, note-taking, translation support, stakeholder liaison, and ongoing methodological refinement, ensuring that each workshop remained aligned with the GA and SAP while evolving responsively to participant and task leads feed backs, event context, and emerging project findings. Taken together, the policy workshops demonstrate how the CoP functioned as the space in which FLIARA's policy evidence was generated, tested and consolidated across work packages.

MONITORING, EVALUATION AND REPORTING

Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting (MER) were core elements of the design and delivery of the FLIARA CoP, as outlined in the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1). The SAP positioned MER not as a compliance formality, but as a continuous, iterative learning mechanism ensuring that each CoP event remained inclusive, ethically grounded, and aligned with the multi-actor methodology and objectives of the task (T4.2) as foreseen in the Grant Agreement (GA). Throughout implementation, MER practices evolved significantly, shaped by participant and partner feedback, Ethics Guardian insights, and the experiential learning gathered across four in-person CoPs and four online CoPs.

The MER plan articulated a set of interlocking components: ethical monitoring, participant feedback, task-level reflection, and consolidated reporting, that together created an adaptive, participant-centred learning system. Ethical oversight was positioned as the first of these pillars, with the SAP mandating continuous attention to wellbeing, inclusion, linguistic accessibility, and equitable participation across all CoP activities. Alongside the Ethics Guardian's event-by-event reflections, the SAP

established a structured participant-feedback system using tailored digital surveys for Ambassadors and general stakeholders, administered through Google Forms in Galway and Mentimeter in Slovenia, Italy, and Sweden. These surveys, accessed via QR codes during closing plenaries and reinforced through follow-up reminders, combined sliding-scale assessments of logistics, inclusivity, and session usefulness with open-ended reflections on takeaways, improvements, and expected impact, ensuring a daily feedback loop consistent with the SAP. Complementing this, all workshop leads applied the Task Description and Task Reflection mechanism: before each CoP they submitted a Task Description outlining objectives, facilitation needs, and methodological requirements for T4.3, T5.2, and T5.3, and after each implementation round they produced a Task Reflection report documenting facilitation conditions, group dynamics, translation needs, and data-quality considerations. Together, these tools created a multilayered monitoring system that captured quantitative trends, qualitative depth, and methodological learning across the full CoP sequence.

Figure 22 Example of feedback surveys covers for the in-person CoP Networking Events

Each online CoP adhered to the same MER structure outlined in the SAP, adapted for a digital environment. Monitoring and evaluation were integrated into all four online events, which expanded beyond what was initially foreseen in the SAP. Each online session followed a structured MER protocol: GDPR-compliant registration and explicit consent for recording ensured ethical data handling; the Ethics Guardian monitored the digital environment to safeguard well-being and inclusivity; and breakout rooms were facilitated to maintain the participatory, multi-actor character of the CoP even in virtual space. Tailored feedback surveys, separate for Ambassadors and other participants, captured both quantitative assessments and qualitative reflections, while consolidated short reports prepared by the WP4 lead documented key insights and adaptations. Over

time, the monitoring process informed several refinements: communication became more targeted and role expectations clearer; preparatory materials were shared earlier to support accessibility, and dedicated support was provided to Ambassadors using the online sessions as preparation spaces ahead of in-person events. Together, these measures ensured that the online FLIARA CoPs were not standalone activities, but integral components of the iterative learning cycle underpinning WP4/T4.2.

Figure 23 Example of feedback received via Mentimeter from the Ambassadors after the final CoP event in Sweden

In practice, these mechanisms were not only implemented but significantly expanded. The Ethics Guardian provided a dedicated event-by-event report, which was systematically reviewed by ECOLISE and the University of Galway and used to inform adjustments before the next CoP. Feedback was collected at each event day through digital tools, using tailored sets of questions that captured both quantitative evaluations and qualitative insights. Reflection templates submitted by task leads documented facilitation conditions, group composition, translation and linguistic needs, and the quality of data generated, creating a cumulative evidence base for methodological improvement. ECOLISE, as lead partner, prepared the detailed event reports included in the Annexes, working collaboratively with the University of Galway, CE, TU Delft and the other task-lead partners, with each host institution reviewing and validating the sections relating to their respective CoP. These reports form the backbone of the cross-event comparison presented in this report, D4.2.

Figure 24 Field visit to the Ödevata Countryside Hotel in Sweden

As implementation progressed, MER directly shaped the evolution of the CoP. Feedback from the Galway University team and the participants led to the introduction of a field visit and more balanced agendas in Ljubljana; lessons from Slovenia informed the creation of an Ambassador-only networking activity, revised visibility-campaign procedures, and stronger multilingual support in Italy; and refinements from Rende improved workshop structuring, spatial arrangements, and communication flows in Sweden. Across all events, MER confirmed strong satisfaction among Ambassadors and stakeholders, while also identifying recurring structural needs such as translation support, more informal networking, and protected spaces for discussing sensitive issues like financial autonomy. These insights not only improved each subsequent CoP but also consolidated coherent documented insights for the final D4.2 report.

Overall, MER became both a governance practice and a learning infrastructure: a mechanism that enabled the FLIARA CoP to remain inclusive, context-sensitive, and responsive to participant needs, while generating reliable, comparable data feeding into WP4, WP5, WP6 and the wider FLIARA policy and visibility work.

FLIARA COP TRANSITION

As outlined in the Grant Agreement and the D4.1 Strategic Action Plan, the FLIARA Community of Practice was designed to continue independently beyond the project's lifetime, supported by the mutual self-empowerment, skills, and connection developed by the 20 Ambassadors throughout the CoP process. We are confident that this will happen since the FLIARA Ambassadors have already taken the initiative of creating a closed WhatsApp group where all 20 were included and where they interact constantly.

Following the final in-person event in Sweden, WP4 Lead (ECOLISE) and the University of Galway facilitated a structured transition phase that enabled Ambassadors to reflect on the CoP's value, identify potential future pathways, and consider forms of voluntary self-organisation appropriate after project closure. The information that has reached the Consortium during this phase is encouraging in the sense of emerging collaboration and innovation projects among the FLIARA Ambassadors, beyond the FLIARA project and organized without the support of the Consortium.

As part of this transition, all project-managed digital spaces were responsibly concluded: the LinkedIn group was closed, access permissions were withdrawn, and all personal data were securely stored or deleted in line with GDPR, the SAP's data governance provisions, and Consortium contractual obligations. With these processes complete, responsibility for any continued interaction rests voluntarily with the Ambassadors and wider participants, supported by the relationships and collective capacities cultivated during the FLIARA CoP.

VISIBILITY CAMPAIGN AND DISSEMINATION

The execution of the FLIARA CoP Networking Events, as outlined in the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1), prominently featured a dedicated visibility and dissemination strategy. This strategy was consistently applied across the four participating host countries (Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, and Sweden) with the primary goal of spotlighting the pivotal role of women in agriculture and rural innovation.

1. SHOWCASING FLIARA AMBASSADORS

A core component of the visibility campaign was the Ambassador Journey, initially established by Galway. This element was central to all four events, providing a dedicated platform to showcase the innovative practices and personal stories of the FLIARA Ambassadors. While specific participants and minor adaptations varied across the four macro-regional events, the core structure and thematic focus remained consistent.

1.1. AMBASSADOR PANEL SESSIONS

Each event included a dedicated session where attendees could meet and engage directly with the Ambassadors. The format involved structured panel discussions and interviews designed to elicit in-depth narratives about their innovation journeys. The structure comprised two main components:

Session Focus Format and Key Topics Spotlighting the FLIARA Ambassadors

Short panel interviews were led by a dedicated Chair of the session. Ambassadors introduced themselves and their innovations (approximately 5 minutes per person). The FLIARA Innovation Journey was an informal, conversational session focusing on one aspect of the Ambassador's personal innovation story, the "FLIARA Innovation Journey". No slides were required, allowing for an organic narrative to be delivered. These sessions were prepared in advance with the support of the Ambassador Buddies.

Thematic Discussion Drivers

The detailed structure for the Innovation Journey was built around six key thematic discussion points. These points were designed by the Project Coordination team to serve as drivers of the discussion, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the challenges and successes faced by women innovators. The themes were adapted to the context of the respective local ambassadors:

Thematic Area Description and Example Questions

- Motivation drivers for starting the innovation (e.g., were you inspired by a desire to advance your career, enhance family well-being, or contribute to sustainability efforts?).
- Decision to act on challenges encountered when initiating the idea/business (e.g., Did you face financial constraints, family-related obstacles, or issues with securing premises?).

- Building a concrete innovation key factors facilitating the transition from idea to reality (e.g., Did you receive assistance from family members, obtain access to financing or grants, or benefit from mentorship?).
- Impacts of your innovation effects on the local community, family, or personal life (e.g., have you seen improvements in community well-being, economic growth, or environmental benefits?).
- Diffusion of innovation strategies for advancing the innovation once operational (e.g., Did you engage in marketing campaigns, expand your product line, or utilise social media?).

Capacity building, importance of networks and support systems for advancing the innovation (e.g., have you found value in joining professional networks, collaborating with industry experts, or receiving support from community organisations?).

Figure 25 The Ambassador Innovation Journey at the four CoP Networking Events

1.2. MEDIA CONTENT PRODUCTION (D6.5 AND TOOLKIT)

To ensure a legacy and maximise visibility, in-depth interviews were recorded with each ambassador present at the events. These assets were leveraged for multiple dissemination channels:

- Video Interviews: These videos were produced to feed into the project's visibility efforts (WP6) and the practical project's toolkit (WP4). They are included in Deliverable 6.5 (D6.5) and published across the FLIARA Project's social media channels.
- Podcasts: The ambassador journey sessions were materialised as FLIARA podcasts, also included in D6.5, uploaded to Spotify, and incorporated into the final version of the FLIARA toolkit. The materials were curated via WP6. This formed part of a content marketing strategy aimed at improving online discoverability (e.g., search engine results for rural European innovation).

2. DISSEMINATION MATERIALS AND CAMPAIGNS

2.1. REGIONAL INNOVATION BOOKLETS

A tangible outcome of the CoP activities was the publication of regional innovation booklets. These materials provided a dedicated space for each hosting region to showcase locally led innovations within the project's four macro-regions. The contents were collaboratively developed by the respective hosting teams, laid out and printed for distribution at each event. In Slovenia and Italy, the booklets were additionally translated into the local language, reflecting an effort by the host teams to improve accessibility and relevance for local audiences and stakeholders. The online versions of the booklets are accessible below:

- Ireland: <https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/SWEDEN-Booklet-Women-Innovators-FLIARA.pdf>
- Slovenia: <https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Booklet-FLIARA-Slovenia.pdf>
- Italy: English version: https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet_Italian.pdf, Italian version: https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Booklet_Italiano.pdf
- Sweden: <https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/SWEDEN-Booklet-Women-Innovators-FLIARA.pdf>

Figure 26 FLIARA Irish Innovators, German Ambassador Anja Frey and Minister Pippa Hackett browse the FLIARA Booklet in Galway

2.2. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT MAILING CAMPAIGNS

In accordance with D4.1, targeted mailing campaigns were executed to gather event attendees. These campaigns, including initial invitations and reminders, strategically integrated visuals featuring FLIARA Ambassadors and local innovators to enhance engagement and relevance. Examples for each region are listed:

- **Ireland:** [Save the date](#), [email invite](#), [Reminder 1](#), [Reminder 2](#)
- **Slovenia:** [Email invite](#), [Reminder 1](#), [Reminder 2](#)
- **Italy:** [Email invite](#), [Reminder 1](#), [Reminder 2](#)
- **Sweden:** [Email invite](#), [Reminder 1](#), [Reminder 2](#)

2.3. ON-SITE AND DIGITAL ASSETS

- **Video Loops:** Animated videos conveying core project messages and key insights were created and displayed at the events, contingent on venue capacity. These materials successfully showcased the work of the project ambassadors, fostering positive public interaction.
- **Posters:** A0-sized posters were distributed and prominently displayed across the four events. These visuals highlighted the journeys and impacts of the 20 Ambassadors central to the CoP, placed in high-traffic areas for maximum exposure.

Figure 27 Screens and posters in Ireland and Sweden

3. CONTENT DISSEMINATION AND REPORTING

3.1. PROJECT DISSEMINATION COMPONENT

The event agendas were designed to incorporate presentations spanning from WP1 to WP3, delivered by the respective WP leaders. This served the dual purpose of contextualising workshops and disseminating FLIARA outputs directly to participating stakeholders across the four macro-regions. The full agendas are available:

- Ireland: <https://fliara.eu/university-of-galway-cop-agenda/>
- Slovenia: <https://fliara.eu/university-of-ljubljana-cop-agenda/>
- Italy: <https://fliara.eu/university-of-calabria-cop-agenda/>
- Sweden: <https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Agenda-CoP-SWEDEN.pdf>

3.2. POST-EVENT JOURNALISTIC REPORTS

Comprehensive journalistic reports covering dissemination activities and overall progress were produced by the project partner CE. These reports, published on the FLIARA Project website and social media channels, included a visual narrative of the sessions and recordings, further extending the impact of the activities and connecting with local communities.

- Ireland: <https://fliara.eu/from-fields-to-future-fliara-champions-womens-innovations-in-rural-europe/>
- Slovenia: <https://fliara.eu/fliaras-2nd-community-of-practice-event-brings-women-led-innovation-to-the-forefront-in-slovenia/>

**Funded by
the European Union**

- Italy: <https://fliara.eu/fliaras-3rd-community-of-practice-in-italy-showcases-female-led-innovation-in-rural-europe/>
- Sweden: <https://fliara.eu/fliara-project-successfully-concludes-4th-community-of-practice-in-vaxjo-sweden/>

The visibility and dissemination elements integrated into the CoP helped the Ambassadors' work resonate across regions and audiences, giving their stories a presence within and beyond the events. By aligning WP4 and WP6 efforts with the commitments set out in the GA and SAP, the project reinforced its central purpose: ensuring that women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas is visible, valued and part of shaping future rural development paths.

THE FLIARA COP: CONNECTION TO THE REST OF PROJECT THE ACTIVITIES

The Community of Practice functioned as a central connective structure within WP4 and across the wider FLIARA architecture. Rather than standing as an isolated set of events, the CoP acted as a continuous interface between research, policy design, visibility, and ethics, ensuring that insights generated through multi-actor transnational engagement flowed into multiple work packages.

Figure 28 Interlinkages between FLIARA Work Packages as per GA

The CoP built directly on the knowledge base established through the three research work packages WP1, WP2 and WP3. Case study findings, innovation journey and national mappings informed the selection of Ambassadors and shaped the themes of each CoP event. In turn, discussions within the CoP served to validate and nuance earlier research results, ensuring that the lived experiences of women innovators remained central to the interpretation of these findings. Details of this research-to-CoP link were described in the introductory and methodological sections.

Concerning internal coherence within WP4, the CoP integrated all core tasks.

- It followed the roadmap established under T4.1, which defined the CoP structure and the engagement pathways linking WP4 activities with the rest of the work packages.
- It created the engagement space that underpinned T4.2 and T4.3.
- It provided the empirical grounding and user feedback loops that informed the Toolkit (T4.4).

- It fed the Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting cycles, with MER findings applied iteratively across all CoP events. Cross-references to these components were present throughout the report, particularly in the overview of events, the MER section and the Toolkit linkages.

Policy design and benchmarking tasks in WP5 relied on inputs generated during CoP workshops, such as scenario exercises, policy mapping and identification of structural challenges faced by women innovators. Each in person CoP included specific WP5 components. Further detail on these contributions appeared in the sections dedicated to event agendas and in Annex 1.

The visibility and dissemination work of WP6 were closely interlinked with the CoP. Event documentation, audio-visual materials, interviews with Ambassadors, articles and social media coverage all emerged from CoP activities. These inputs fed directly into the project's Visibility Campaign, as foreseen in the GA and reiterated in the SAP, where CoP events were identified as primary generators of communication content. These outputs were developed collaboratively with WP6 partners and contributed to D6.2 and ongoing communication actions. Evidence of this collaboration was reflected in the visibility and dissemination section.

The CoP operated under WP8 guidance for ethics and data protection. The presence of the Ethics Guardian at events, informed consent procedures and attention to well-being were all embedded into the CoP process. The Ethics and Data Management section of this report provided full detail on this alignment.

In this configuration, WP4 was implemented as foreseen in the Grant Agreement and the Strategic Action Plan: as the coordinating backbone that links the project's research, policy, communication and ethical components into a coherent whole. The cross-work-package collaboration described in this section was not an accessory, but a structural requirement for meeting FLIARA's objectives of generating integrated evidence, producing actionable policy pathways, and building a shared understanding across partners. By functioning as the central interface through which insights, methods and outputs circulated, WP4 strengthened internal coherence and ensured that the project advanced as a unified architecture rather than as parallel strands of activity. In practice, the depth of collaboration achieved across WP1 to WP8 often exceeded what was anticipated in the GA, with WP4 enabling continuous alignment, iterative learning and coordinated delivery across milestones. This integrative function demonstrates the relevance of the CoP structure for achieving the project's overarching goals and confirms WP4's contribution to the strategic vision set out for FLIARA.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT OF THE FLIARA COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The Community of Practice generated a set of interconnected outcomes that sit within the project architecture foreseen in the GA and clarified in the SAP. These outcomes reflect not only what the CoP produced, but how it worked: through iterative gatherings, shared governance practices, multi-actor engagement and careful attention to ethics and wellbeing. The section below organises these outcomes across the main domains where effects were visible inside and beyond WP4.

OUTCOMES FOR AMBASSADORS AND INNOVATIVE WOMEN

The CoP created conditions for the innovative women participants to strengthen their confidence and sense of legitimacy in local and EU settings where innovation is often structurally constrained. Through in person encounters and the closing online session, Ambassadors reported feeling more grounded and supported in their roles. The macro-regional meetings and online gatherings generated transnational peer networks that continued informally through a self-organised WhatsApp group. New skills and knowledge were developed through cybersecurity training, policy work and funding sessions shaped in response to the Ambassadors' stated needs. The visibility tools emerging from CoP activities provided recognition without displacing their agency, presenting Ambassadors as knowledge holders and central actors in rural sustainable development and agriculture, rather than recipients of support.

Figure 29 FLIARA Ambassadors during the celebration of the FLIARA CoP (4th CoP Networking Event in Sweden)

TRANSFORMATIONS IN RELATIONSHIPS, SOLIDARITY AND MUTUAL SUPPORT

The FLIARA Community of Practice played a central role in enabling the project's visibility work, as foreseen in the Grant Agreement and operationalised through the Strategic Action Plan. Audio-visual materials, interviews, communication outputs and local media engagement were generated in direct relation to CoP activities and fed into the Visibility Campaign developed under WP6. Through these processes, women-led innovation was presented as a collective and interconnected field of practice, embedded in wider rural and agricultural innovation landscapes rather than as individual or exceptional cases. Public-facing moments, including open online events and the Final Conference organised under WP6, reinforced this approach by creating spaces where participants could speak in their own terms and situate their experiences within broader policy and societal debates.

Over time, the FLIARA CoP became a space of relational learning in which Ambassadors could share their personal experiences and gendered constraints through sustained interaction, supporting mutual recognition, trust, and a growing collective capacity to navigate rural and agricultural innovation contexts. This dynamic was particularly visible during the online CoP events, where recurring exchanges and shared points of reference enabled collective sense-making and mutual recognition. As relationships deepened, discussions increasingly reflected a networked understanding of how women navigate rural development, agriculture and institutional environments, allowing strategies and perspectives to circulate horizontally across contexts. Trust and solidarity were reinforced through the iterative rhythm of the CoP and the continuity of engagement, supported by monitoring and reflection practices and the presence of the Ethics Guardian, underscoring that wellbeing, care and relational safety were embedded features of the CoP's design.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO POLICY LEARNING AND DESIGN

The CoP provided WP5 with insights that informed the policy tasks of benchmarking, scenario exercises and the development of future policy directions. Workshops at each in person CoP produced concrete inputs, including naming structural issues related to land access, finance, administrative burdens and formal decision-making spaces. These insights strengthened the gender benchmarking and national policy briefs and helped ensure that policy outputs remained connected to lived realities. The CoP thus served as a site where emerging policy ideas could be collected and confronted with diverse practices and contexts before being refined further.

METHODOLOGICAL AND GOVERNANCE OUTCOMES WITHIN WP4

The CoP functioned as a form of “living infrastructure”, understood in this report as an enabling structure for coordination, learning and adaptation across WP4, with MER cycles guiding adaptation from Ireland, through Slovenia, Italy and Sweden. These iterations generated methodological clarity and concrete improvements, such as expanding travel opportunities, revising agendas for more field-based learning,

improving language accessibility, creating Ambassador-only spaces and reinforcing the Buddy-based support. Ethics were embedded in the CoP through direct accompaniment, consent processes and structured attention to participant well-being, turning WP8, Ethics requirements into an active governance practice rather than a compliance layer. The CoP was effective because it combined structured inputs, collaborative workshops, field visits and informal interaction, creating a learning environment in which knowledge exchange, reflection and relationship-building could reinforce each other over time.

VISIBILITY AND NARRATIVE CHANGE

The CoP functioned as a central platform for the project's visibility work, as foreseen in the GA and reiterated in the SAP, alongside other project activities such as the WP3 interviews and WP6 communication outputs. Audio-visual materials, interviews, communication content and local press were generated in direct relation to CoP activities and fed into the Visibility Campaign developed under WP6.

Through its collective formats and public-facing moments, the CoP provided a space in which women-led innovation could be articulated, re-framed and recognised as part of a shared, interconnected field of practice, situated within wider rural and agricultural innovation landscapes. Rather than producing fragmented or individualised representations, CoP activities enabled each innovation journey to be positioned within common challenges, patterns and trajectories across regions. Public-facing moments, including open online events and the Final Conference organised under WP6, reinforced this approach by foregrounding women's voices and situating them as relevant actors within broader societal and policy conversations about rural and agriculture sustainable innovation.

PROJECT-WIDE IMPACTS AND SYNERGIES

The CoP created a shared space where findings from WP1 to WP3 could be tested, questioned and enriched, linking early research tasks to later policy and visibility outputs. WP4 benefited from this circulation through a coherent methodological trajectory visible in the Toolkit (D4.4) and its replication potential. WP5 drew directly on CoP workshops to shape its policy learning and policy proposals. WP6 integrated CoP-generated content into communication and dissemination. WP8 used the CoP to ground ethics in lived practice. Through these linkages, the CoP strengthened the whole project architecture, ensuring it worked as one ecosystem rather than as loosely connected tasks.

LONGER-TERM AND POST-PROJECT EFFECTS

Some effects of the CoP extend beyond the project period. Ambassadors will likely maintain their network through the WhatsApp group and through emerging collaborations. Skills and contacts developed through the CoP will continue to support innovative women's continued engagement with institutions, funders and local actors. The documented process, MER cycles and reflections in D4.2 and D4.4 also position the CoP as a transferable design for future EU projects and rural initiatives, adapted to different contexts while retaining ethical safeguards.

LIMITS, TENSIONS AND CRITICAL REFLECTIONS

The CoP faced structural constraints that were generally mitigated: uneven participation linked to language, care responsibilities, travel limitations and time scarcity; mixed perceptions of some visibility and workshop elements; and low engagement in asynchronous formats such as LinkedIn. These tensions highlight the need for more co-created agendas, differentiated support measures and careful consideration of which digital infrastructures actually serve rural organising. Naming these limits is important for the integrity of the project and the future use of the FLIARA CoP methodology.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of the FLIARA Community of Practice unfolded within the wider ambitions set out in the Grant Agreement and the Strategic Action Plan: to recognise and advance women's central role in sustainable, inclusive and future-oriented rural and agriculture innovation. WP4 was designed as a shared project infrastructure that could hold these ambitions in practice by creating a transnational space where learning, dialogue and collaboration could take root. Through the CoP, this intention became a lived set of practices: partners worked together to reflect on gendered rural inequalities, connect innovation with sustainability and rural/agriculture challenges, and link local experiences to European policy contexts. By enabling research, policy exploration, visibility work and ethical grounding to circulate through shared encounters, rather than remaining in separate streams, WP4 helped FLIARA operate as a coherent innovation ecosystem able to engage with the political, social, economic and environmental pressures shaping European rural futures.

Across the CoP events, FLIARA demonstrated the added value of working through shared integrated practice. Bringing research tasks, policy workshops, visibility activities and ethical support into the same spaces allowed partners to test ideas together, adjust methods in real time, and respond collectively to feedback from women innovators and other stakeholders. This mode of working strengthened connections between work packages through sustained dialogue across research, policy and communication, producing outputs that were coherent, grounded and mutually reinforcing.

A defining feature of the CoP was its evolution as a living infrastructure, shaped through the rhythm of Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting. The continuous cycle of implementation, observation, reflection and adaptation influenced the design and atmosphere of every event from Galway to Växjö. Adjustments were introduced in response to real conditions and participant needs: expanded travel opportunities, improved language accessibility measures, more purposeful spaces for relationship-building, and the embedding of ethical care as a central governance practice. This adaptability deepened both inclusiveness and integrity, enabling the CoP to remain grounded in the realities of transnational participation.

Through this process, the CoP made a clear contribution to FLIARA's strategic objectives. It strengthened the project's commitment to generating integrated evidence by placing research findings into contact with lived experience, with women innovators actively contributing to the co-production of knowledge across research, policy and practice. It enriched policy work by creating participatory spaces where structural issues could be named and carried forward into benchmarking, scenario building and policy brief development. It fed the project's visibility efforts with materials that reflected the wider realities shaping rural innovation. It also advanced the broader ambition of inclusive rural futures by treating collaboration, mutual learning and shared inquiry as conditions for genuine sustainability.

At the same time, the CoP delivered outcomes that exceeded what was initially envisioned in the formal planning documents. Adaptive decisions allowed Ambassadors to participate in multiple events, broadening the transnational dimension of the network. The emergence of self-organised continuation through shared communication channels and early collaborations demonstrated that the connections formed within WP4 will very likely be extended beyond the funded period. The documented methodology, MER framework and ethical practices now form a coherent approach that can be transferred into other EU projects or rural initiatives, positioning WP4 as a contributor not only to FLIARA's outputs but also to wider conversations on gender-based approaches to rural sustainability.

Finally, the CoP generated critical learnings that will be valuable for future work. Some structural constraints remained difficult to overcome, like uneven participation linked to language, care responsibilities, time and travel limitations; the challenge of making digital spaces feel as meaningful as in-person encounters; and varied assessments of which activities best supported participants' needs. These tensions underscore the ongoing importance of accessibility, differentiated support and co-created agendas. Acknowledging these limits strengthens the transparency and credibility of the FLIARA work and provides a solid foundation for more grounded methodological design in future transnational initiatives.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – EVENT REPORT: 1ST FLIARA COP NETWORKING EVENT – GALWAY, IRELAND, 1 –2 JULY 2024

This report is to assist in the monitoring, evaluation and reflection of the FLIARA CoP, as laid out in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP). A final summary of these results and measures taken due to them will be included in deliverable D4.2 Report on CoP Networking events, which will be delivered by December 2025 (M36).

The ambassadors' well-being was monitored throughout the implementation of the Galway CoP. The FLIARA ethics mentor uses their role throughout the project to observe, monitor and support the well-being of the Ambassadors. For the purposes of this element of the project and for ease of identification for the Women Ambassadors, the title of *FLIARA CoP Ethics Guardian* has been developed. The Ethics Guardian participated in the Galway CoP events and wrote a report, which is supported by feedback from the ambassadors themselves and other stakeholders that participated.

The report prepared by the Ethics Guardian after the Galway CoP event was analysed to allow for adjustments and improvements for the following networking events in Slovenia, Italy and Sweden. An analysis of the 4 reports and measures taken after each of them will be compiled within the final report. All feedback received by the Ethics Guardian during the FLIARA CoP was anonymised, analysed and compiled to be included in the deliverable D4.2 Report on CoP Networking events.

This document outlines what happened at the Galway CoP event, it includes the full agenda and a more detailed description of both days. It outlines the methodologies used for selecting participants and gives final breakdown of stakeholders and participants who participated. It outlines the feedback process activated, including descriptions of the structure of the questions asked. It gives overviews of the feedback from the different participant groups: ambassadors, and stakeholders (consortium and general stakeholders), as well as feedback from key parts of the consortium team including task leaders for the workshops and the communications team. It concludes with key takeaways and suggestions from the Galway CoP to be shared with the hosts of future CoP events.

COP EVENT 1: GALWAY 1-2 JULY 2024

The first FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) Networking event happened in Galway, Ireland, on Monday 1st and Tuesday 2nd of July 2024.

Day 1 happened at the O'Donoghue Centre of the University of Galway, beginning with refreshments and a networking event in the theatre space. This was followed by the Ambassador Innovation Journey.

Day 2 had a day of events in the historic Quadrangle building of University of Galway, with workshops focused on policy development, participatory scenario development, and future foresight.

While the FLIARA consortium had an assembly during the first half of Day 1, the ambassadors and some stakeholders were brought on a historical walking tour of Galway city.

83 registered participants: 6 FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors, 31 Consortium Members, 3 FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board Members, 9 policy/decision-makers, 20 Innovative Irish Women, 14 other stakeholders.

Figure 30 Group photo during the 1st FLIARA CoP Networking Event in Galway, Ireland, 1-2 of July 2024

DESCRIPTION OF GALWAY COP ACTIVITIES

COP EVENT 1: GALWAY 1-2 JULY 2024

The first FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) Networking event happened in Galway, Ireland, on Monday 1st and Tuesday 2nd of July 2024.

Table 1 Galway CoP Agenda

FLIARA CoP Networking Event
Day 1 – Monday 1 st July 2024
Registration, 3.30 pm - 4.00 pm
• Tea and Coffee, O'Donoghue Centre, University of Galway
Networking, 4.00 pm - 5.00 pm

- Networking & Refreshments at the O'Donoghue Centre, University of Galway
- Launch of the FLIARA CoP, 5.00 pm – 6.45 pm**
- Welcome by Associate Professor Maura Farrell, Project Coordinator.
 - Opening address by Minister Pippa Hackett, Minister of State for Land Use and Biodiversity, Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine.
 - Overview of FLIARA by Associate Professor Maura Farrell
 - Panel discussion moderated by Sally-Ann Barrett, Multimedia Journalist with Freeway Media and Communications.
 - Panel 1 - FLIARA Ambassadors: Mieke Elzenga (The Netherlands), Annette Harberink (The Netherlands), Bláthnaid Gallagher (Ireland), Ursula Kelly (Ireland), Alexandra Larsson (Sweden), Anja Frey (Germany).
 - Panel 2 - Minister Pippa Hackett, MEP Maria Walsh, and representatives from the FLIARA, SWIFT and GRASS CEILING Horizon Europe projects.
- Evening BBQ, 7.00 pm – 9.00 pm**
- Sult Bar

Day 2 – Tuesday 2nd of July 2024.

Registration, 8.30 am - 9.00 am

- Tea and Coffee, O'Donoghue Centre, University of Galway
- 9.00 - 09.10am**
- Welcome, Introduction and Overview of the Day, Associate Professor Maura Farrell
- 9.10 - 09.50am**
- FLIARA Overview
- 09.50 - 10.30am**
- Ambassador Innovation Journey
- 10.30 - 10.45am**
- Coffee Break
- 10.45 - 12.15pm**
- Future Foresight Workshop
- 12.15 - 12.30pm**
- Feedback from Workshop Breakout Groups
- 12.30 - 12.45pm**
- Reflections from the FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board
- 12.45 - 1.45pm**
- Lunch
- 1.45 - 2.05pm**
- FLIARA Policy Context
- 2.05 - 2.45pm**
- Ambassador Innovation Journey
- 2.45 - 4.15pm**
- FLIARA Policy Workshop Sessions
Two parallel group sessions – group details provided on registration
- Aula Maxima (Ground floor)
- Emily Anderson Theatre (1st floor)
- 4.15 - 4.30pm**
- FLIARA CoP Assembly
Both groups re-convene in Aula Maxima and feedback on parallel sessions
Tea and coffee available
- 4.30 - 4.45pm**
- Reflections from the FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board
- 4.45 - 5.00pm**
- Wrap up
Associate Professor Maura Farrell

Workshop Descriptions

Guided by the GA, the SAP outlines that one of the two main purposes of The FLIARA CoP is to develop an interchange platform for multi-actor exchanges, via a series of four EU workshops with all relevant key stakeholders. The SAP outlines how Workshops are a key part of the FLIARA conceptual framework to “explore policy benchmarking, participatory scenario development for policy and broader policy dialogues. This will allow the exploration of the hypothesis and leverage point “Transforming policy and governance towards gender equality” and how “Governance solutions can provide opportunities, incentives, and support for female innovators”. In addition, by FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors and other women leading innovations in agriculture and rural areas being at the centre of the FLIARA CoP Network this also links to leverage point “Women in Decision-Making” and supports “Increasing women’s opportunities to participate in decisions concerning their lives”.

During the Galway CoP event, 3 workshops were included, that feed into three different tasks in 2 different work packages, these tasks build on and feed into wider work packages in the following way, as outlined in the GA:

Table 2 FLIARA CoP Workshop description

Work package WP4 – FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Task 4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design
Task 4.3 will continue the work on benchmarking EU and National Policy and Legal Frameworks by assessing the work carried out in WP1 and the results of case studies from WP3 and devising a strategy to engage participants at the four Community of Practice Networking events via focus groups and workshops to discuss the findings and ascertain key issues to be brought forward to the policy design and assessment workshops. These focus groups/workshops will be held alongside the Community of Practice Networking events. This task will also play a role in organising participatory scenario building exercises, which will be finalised in WP5.
Work package WP5 – Policy Design and Assessment
Task 5.2: Policy practice discussions
This task will embrace a multi-actor approach through a policy practice dialogue taking place at the four Community of Practice Networking events (WP4). The purpose is to break down disciplinary silos and engage users and experts in exploring lessons learned and outcomes, policy, institutional and other challenges encountered across FLIARA. Exploring this in four regional settings ensures that diverse regional contexts will also be observed. The outcome of this task will ensure more end-user effective policy, in addition to informing recommendations for structural changes of governance frameworks at different levels and inform national policy environments.
Task 5.3: Develop new policy proposals
Conduct a series of focus groups with key stakeholders, namely women leading farming and rural innovations, policymakers and other relevant stakeholders in a process of Participatory Scenario Development. The qualitative and participatory techniques applied in a Participatory Scenario Development exercise encourage discussion, deliberation, and the exchange of thoughts. The process also provides a framework to support future decisions and stimulate engagement in the process of change. The University of Galway and TU Delft will lead on the Participatory Scenario Development, with participation from other partners.

Following the steps outlined in the SAP, each of the workshop leads added objectives for the workshop in the “FLIARA CoP task content builder” and in the lead-up to the event, they collaborated with the host to divide up the list of guests as fairly as possible, connecting ambassadors, policymakers and other stakeholders. The timing format was copied from how it was in Galway, with TASK 5.3 happening on its own and tasks T4.3 & T5.2 happen simultaneously in two different rooms. The 2nd “Workshop, T4.3, was a Focus Group. Workshop leads defined themes and needs (how many tables, what group size, what extra resources needed).

Communication for the Event

In preparation for the Community of Practice event, CE coordinated the communication and outreach activities, ensuring clear, timely, and targeted engagement with stakeholders. A Strategic Action Plan guided the communications process, beginning with the creation of suggested stakeholder lists, to which all partners contributed. CE then refined and organized the final participant selection.

A structured communication flow was implemented, including the design and distribution of promotional materials, agenda, travel guide, and registration forms. Email invitations were sent out alongside three follow-up reminders, participation confirmation emails, and a final logistics email containing all relevant information. An Ambassadors’ Guide was also prepared to support their participation and visibility.

To facilitate easy access to event resources, a Linktree was created and added to the FLIARA website. Detailed workshop descriptions and a general event overview were shared in advance, enhancing transparency and participant preparedness.

During the event, a visually engaging FLIARA booklet featuring all 30 Irish innovators was distributed to participants. A poster exhibition presented the FLIARA Ambassadors’ work, and the sessions from July 1st were live streamed via the FLIARA YouTube channel, significantly extending the event’s visibility and impact.

Day 1: LAUNCH OF THE FLIARA COP AT UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

Galway, Ireland, July 1–2, 2024. The FLIARA Project celebrated its inaugural Community of Practice (CoP) event, bringing together passionate individuals dedicated to supporting and accelerating women-led innovation in rural areas. Held from July 1st to July 2nd, this event marked a noteworthy achievement for the project, showcasing the remarkable progress made since its launch in January 2023.

FLIARA, or Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas, is a Horizon Europe project aimed at creating a European-wide rural innovation ecosystem. The project focuses on enhancing the recognition and support of women’s contributions in agriculture through a robust network and a high-impact visibility campaign.

The FLIARA Project’s consortium has conducted extensive case studies, identifying 200 innovative practices across ten European countries: Ireland, the Netherlands, Germany,

the Czech Republic, Slovenia, Sweden, Finland, Spain, Romania, and Italy. From this impressive pool, 20 FLIARA ambassadors have been chosen. During the first CoP event, the initial group of six ambassadors were presented to a wider audience and stakeholders.

The CoP event featured the introduction of the first group of FLIARA Ambassadors—exceptional women innovators selected from across the project’s case study countries. These ambassadors are at the forefront of demonstrating the innovative capacity of women in farming and rural areas, contributing to the project’s objectives of promoting sustainability across environmental, economic, social, and cultural dimensions.

During the first day, the event was officially launched with over 80 attendees at the O’Donoghue Centre of the University of Galway. Project Coordinator, Associate Professor Maura Farrell, welcomed all participants and provided an introduction and overview of the day. The opening address was delivered by Minister Pippa Hackett, Minister of State for Land Use and Biodiversity at the Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine in Ireland emphasising the government’s commitment to gender equality in agriculture, acknowledging the crucial role of women in driving entrepreneurial and innovative activities in rural areas.

“Supporting women farmers will remain a key priority. For me personally, professionally, and within the government, gaining insight into the lived experiences of women working and living in agriculture in Ireland will inform our approach to implementing effective policies and supports to encourage and recognise the role of women in the sustainable future of agriculture and rural life in Ireland,” Minister Hackett stated.

The European Commission’s Commitment to Gender Equality

The event also featured participation from the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development of the European Commission. Equality Coordinator for Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, Margaret Bateson-Missen, expressed her gratitude for the FLIARA Project and highlighted how the European Commission is working to reduce gender gaps across Europe.

A highlight of the event was the panel discussion moderated by Sally-Ann Barrett, a multimedia journalist with Freeway Media and Communications. The panel featured the FLIARA Ambassadors: Mieke Elzenga and Annette Harberink (The Netherlands), Bláthnaid Gallagher and Ursula Kelly (Ireland), Alexandra Larsson (Sweden), and Anja Frey (Germany).

A Landmark Event for Rural Innovation

The discussion also included contributions from Member of the European Parliament (MEP) Maria Walsh, Steve Dolan, CEO of Galway Rural Development along with Maura Farrell and Muireann Prendergast Postdoctoral Researcher, School of Humanities, SETU Waterford and member of the Grass Ceiling Project. They explored how research can inform policies and best practices in agriculture and rural development, highlighting the importance of gender equality in these fields.

MEP Maria Walsh emphasised the importance of translating good ideas into policy to improve the lives of people in those areas, especially women and those in agriculture.

Recognising the need to learn from successful practices in other European countries, she expressed her commitment to working on these issues and acknowledged there is more work to be done.

Figure 31 FLIARA Ambassador Innovation Journey. L-R: Moderator Sally-Ann Barrett, Bláthnaid Gallagher and Ursula Kelly (Ireland), Annette Harberink and Mieke Elzenga (The Netherlands), Alexandra Larsson (Sweden), and Anja Frey (Germany).

Day 2: FLIARA WORKSHOPS AT UNIVERSITY OF GALWAY

On the second day, the event continued with workshops focused on policy development, participatory scenario development, and future foresight. These sessions brought together key actors and stakeholders to collaboratively address the challenges and opportunities for women-led innovation in rural areas.

Reflections from the FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board were shared by Steven Dolan and Inge Van Oost, Policy Officer AKIS coordination and CAP networks at the European Commission, wrapping up the two-day event with a forward-looking perspective on the potential of women-led innovations in rural areas.

“The FLIARA project is spotlighting women across Europe who are positively impacting the sustainability and development of rural areas and farming. Our FLIARA Ambassadors embody these efforts, and in showcasing their innovative approaches, we can learn from their experiences and create an ecosystem that empowers more women to become agents of change in rural and farming communities,” stated Project Coordinator, Associate Professor Maura Farrell.

The FLIARA CoP is a key element of the project’s visibility campaign, which aims to boost the role of women in agriculture and rural areas. The campaign seeks to inspire

and empower more women to become agents of change in their communities by spotlighting the innovative achievements of the ambassadors.

FLIARA remains committed to challenging gender norms and stereotypes, increasing gender consciousness, and recognising the economic value women bring to rural economies and development. The project will continue its efforts with upcoming CoP events in Slovenia, Italy, and Sweden, where more ambassadors will be introduced.

FEEDBACK FROM THE GALWAY COP

Feedback from the Galway Community of Practice (CoP) was collected through two tailored Google Forms, developed in line with the Strategic Action Plan (SAP) guidelines and integrating input from both the event host (University of Galway) and the Ethics Guardian. Separate surveys were designed for FLIARA Ambassadors and stakeholders, reflecting their distinct roles and experiences during the event. Both forms were distributed at the end of the two-day CoP and followed up with a reminder email post-event to increase response rates.

Table 3 Registered Stakeholders & Feedback for both days Galway CoP

Type	Number	Participated in Workshops	Feedback Day 1	Feedback Day 2
Ambassadors	7		15 (see note)	6
Innovators	8		3	3
Consortium Partners	30		24	16
SAB	0		0	0
Stakeholders	43		11	4
Total	78		53	29

Table 4 Stakeholder responses, Days 1 & 2

	Day 1		Day 2	
Stakeholder type	Responses	Group %	Responses	Group %
Consortium Member	24	65	16	73
Policy or Decision Maker	0	0	0	0
Researcher	3	8	2	9
LAG member	4	11	1	5
Journalist	0	0	0	0
Activist	3	8	0	0
Woman Innovator	3	8	3	14
Total	38	100%	23	100%

Feedback questions and scoring

The surveys included seven structured questions. Most were sliding scale items (1 = unsatisfactory / 5 = excellent or 1 = no likely positive impact / 5 = large likely positive impact), enabling quick evaluation of logistical aspects, the usefulness of specific activities, and the overall experience. These quantitative questions covered areas such as communication, venue, agenda, social programme, accommodation, and specific sessions (e.g. policy workshops, networking, innovation journey, and the foresight activity).

To complement this, several open-ended questions invited deeper qualitative feedback. These explored:

- What participants found most and least useful
- Suggestions for improving future FLIARA events
- Main personal takeaways
- Broader comments on the project and CoP

This mixed-methods approach provided both evaluative insight and constructive direction for future activities

AMBASSADOR EXPERIENCE AND ETHICS OVERVIEW

According to the report provided by the designated Ethics Guardian, the FLIARA Community of Practice event held in Galway was carried out in full alignment with the project's ethical standards. Ambassadors were meaningfully engaged across both days, receiving ample time and space to contribute their insights in all sessions, including policy workshops and informal exclusive gatherings. Their active participation, leadership in discussions, and visible comfort and enthusiasm reflected the inclusive, respectful, and empowering environment created by the organizers. No ethical concerns were observed, and the event was praised by the Ambassadors for its warm atmosphere, high-quality facilitation, and support for ambassador wellbeing and collaboration.

Ambassador Feedback

Four out of six FLIARA Ambassadors responded to the Galway CoP feedback survey, giving the event overwhelmingly positive evaluations. All respondents rated their overall experience as excellent (5/5). Organisational aspects such as the agenda, inclusivity, accommodation, logistics, and the social programme received top marks, with only minor variation in communication and food ratings.

Ambassadors found the Future Foresight Policy Workshop especially impactful (100% rated 5), alongside strong appreciation for networking opportunities, shared experiences, and knowledge exchange. While panel discussions and policy workshops were well received, a few noted the desire for deeper dialogue and clearer focus. Differences in national contexts and language barriers were acknowledged as occasional challenges to integration.

All respondents indicated that becoming part of the FLIARA CoP, engaging with the consortium, and connecting with fellow Ambassadors had a strong positive impact on their innovation practices. Suggestions for improvement included shorter pre-event communication, increased Ambassador visibility, and greater policy-maker participation. The main takeaway: the need for women to confidently assert their contributions to rural innovation, supported by peer networks like FLIARA. Overall, the event was described as empowering, well-organised, and deeply appreciated.

STAKEHOLDER FEEDBACK

The Galway Community of Practice (CoP) event received overwhelmingly positive feedback from stakeholders, with 18 responses highlighting its inspiring atmosphere, strong organisation, and value for networking and learning. All responses for all questions were positive (3 or above, with 1 being unsatisfactory and 5 being excellent). 77.4% of the respondents rated the event overall as excellent. The most appreciated aspects included the storytelling by female innovators, small group discussions using vision cards, and the creative foresight workshop. Day 2's networking session was especially praised. Participants valued the safe and empowering space for sharing lived experiences and policy reflections.

Some areas for improvement were noted, including a call for more visuals during ambassador presentations, stronger engagement during parallel policy workshops, and more clarity for new attendees. Stakeholders suggested future events include more field-based activities, increased involvement from policymakers, and follow-up mechanisms to track impact.

The main takeaways included renewed motivation, deeper understanding of women-led rural innovation across Europe, and the importance of inclusive, evidence-informed policy. The event's structure, energy, and facilitation were consistently lauded, with many expressing enthusiasm for ongoing involvement in the FLIARA network.

FEEDBACK FROM TASK LEADERS

Task Reflection T4.3 (Lead Partner: ECOLISE)

Task 4.3 was successfully implemented during the Galway CoP event, meeting both project and participant expectations. The focus group sessions proved highly effective in fostering collaboration and generating rich insights, particularly regarding policy gaps and opportunities identified by engaged practitioners and ambassadors. Participants demonstrated deep contextual awareness and a strong interest in influencing public policy.

Key co-created outputs include the Focus Group Guide, detailed session notes, and preliminary analysis that feeds into the public benchmarking report (D4.3). The main lessons learned emphasize the importance of early logistical preparation, facilitator and

notetaker training, and optimized group size (maximum 8 participants per table). Future sessions would benefit from quieter, dedicated spaces and longer time slots (1.5 hours) to support deeper dialogue and more structured data collection.

Task Reflection T5.2 (Lead Partner: TU Delft)

Task 5.2 facilitated dynamic policy practice discussions during the Galway CoP event, enabling multi-actor engagement and knowledge co-creation around the challenges and opportunities facing female-led innovation in rural areas. Through roundtable dialogues, participants—including innovators, entrepreneurs, researchers, and policymakers—identified shared barriers such as access to funding, bureaucratic complexity, and limited rural broadband. The collaborative format supported the emergence of actionable policy suggestions, including phased funding models, improved inclusivity measures, and clearer, more accessible information.

Key outcomes included practical policy problems and recommendations and cross-regional insights that will inform future FLIARA advocacy and CoP events. The methods employed proved effective, supported by strong facilitation and pre-event preparation. Suggestions for improvement included providing translation support to enhance inclusivity and sharing materials in advance. The task's inclusive and structured format succeeded in gathering grounded policy input and reaffirmed the importance of considering regional diversity in shaping future EU rural innovation policies. The format of note taking was good, but too extensive. Because of the limited amount of time, a thorough analysis of the problem was not possible. The outcomes showed similarities in topics.

Task Reflection T5.3 (Lead Partners: University of Galway & University of Turku)

Task 5.3 piloted a Participatory Scenario Development workshop during the Galway CoP, aimed at co-creating future-oriented policy proposals to support women-led innovation in rural areas. Using a set of 22 vision cards developed from WP2 findings, participants collaboratively explored which futures women could meaningfully shape and what policy measures would be needed to realise them. Eight cards were selected and discussed, with “rural image” and “funding models” proving most popular—suggesting priority themes for policy exploration.

The session revealed diverse and context-specific strategies for policy intervention, highlighting training, funding mechanisms, networking, and gender-sensitive governance as key enablers. The methodology effectively encouraged collaboration, though refinements—such as organizing cards thematically—could support deeper engagement. Outcomes from this pilot will inform the refinement of the method and workshop design for future CoP events. Results also contribute to Deliverable D5.2 and will be further enriched through integration with findings from WPs 1 and 3.

LESSONS LEARNED AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The scoring for the Galway CoP event was high with most responses coming in between the 4 and 5 mark. The ambassadors were well taken care of, as the Ethics Guardian attested to. Regarding How CoP participants rated the event, the feedback covered four main areas. Here are the main points shared:

KEY STRENGTHS

- **Ambassador Innovation Journeys** were a central element of the event, making women innovators' experiences visible and legible through situated narratives that connected personal trajectories to wider rural and agricultural innovation contexts.
- The **Future Foresight policy workshop** created a generative and empowering space for collective reflection, combining knowledge exchange with creative methods to imagine regenerative and just rural futures.
- The event offered sustained opportunities for dialogue across multiple actor groups, enabling women innovators, researchers, policy actors and other stakeholders to engage directly and learn from one another's perspectives.
- **Parallel workshop sessions** proved particularly valuable, allowing for in-depth discussion of cross-cutting challenges affecting different sectors represented in the project. The thematic focus, guiding questions and facilitation design supported meaningful exchange despite the inherent complexity of multi-actor settings.
- The discussions highlighted the structural relevance of gender in rural and agricultural innovation, while also revealing how public understandings of gender remain uneven or constrained across contexts.
- The sessions demonstrated that successful innovation pathways are possible, while also acknowledging persistent challenges. Crucially, they showed how peer exchange with experienced women innovators can offer concrete strategies, reassurance and support in navigating these challenges.
- Participants noted the breadth and depth of expertise present in the room, alongside the recognition that similar policy-related constraints are experienced across sectors, reinforcing the value of shared, cross-sectoral dialogue.

AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

- Informal social moments, such as the BBQ, felt less accessible for participants who did not already know others, suggesting the need for clearer facilitation or lighter structuring to support inclusion.
- Ambassador Innovation Journey presentations could be strengthened through the use of **visual or audio-visual materials** showcasing the Ambassadors' work, reducing repetition with earlier sessions while supporting engagement for participants who were not present at the opening event.

- A **less densely packed agenda**, potentially spread across two half-days, could allow more space for reflection, interaction and engagement with the surrounding rural context.
- Small-group workshops were valued, but their effectiveness depended strongly on facilitation. Clear moderation is needed to ensure equitable participation and that all voices are heard.
- Workshop sessions would benefit from **sharper thematic focus**, clearer introductions to content, and more explicit framing of objectives to support deeper discussion.
- The inclusion of **field visits** was identified as an important improvement, offering opportunities to better understand the local rural context, practices and cultural setting of the host region.
- Additional **networking opportunities**, both formal and informal, were requested to strengthen relationship-building across participants and stakeholder groups.

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

FLIARA Event Report

- From Fields to Future: FLIARA Champions Women's Innovations in Rural Europe <https://fliara.eu/from-fields-to-future-fliara-champions-womens-innovations-in-rural-europe/>

VIDEO:

- FLIARA Community of Practice (Galway, Ireland) - 1st July 2024 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U5mx06A1pRQ>

1st FLIARA CoP Event information on the FLIARA website:

- FLIARA Linktree <https://fliara.eu/fliara-galway-cop/>

Public LinkedIn posts:

- FLIARA: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/fliara-project_womeninagriculture-ruralinnovation-fliaraeu-activity-7214652285870587905-XECL/
- Maria Walsh, Member of the European Parliament: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mariawalsh_mep-midlandsnorthwest-activity-7214316506841575424-jfH/
- Aoife Noone, Irish Innovator: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aoife-noone_fliara-galway-europe-activity-7214348657721049089-hSzz
- ECOLISE: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ecolise_fliara-communityled-systemchange-activity-7214150347651497985-lnSW
- Galway Rural Development Clg:
- Day 1: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/galway-rural_fliara-uofg-fliaracop-activity-7213661217993732097-SwvL

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- Day 2: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/galway-rural_fliara-fliaraeu-womeninagri-activity-7214174975946076161-C6St
- FLIARA - Community of Practice, digital space on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9833161/>
- Local coverage of the Irish CoP: <https://www3.farmersjournal.ie/careers/education/agri-careers-fliara-celebrates-rural-women-innovators-825940>

ANNEX 2 – EVENT REPORT: 2ND FLIARA COP NETWORKING EVENT – LJUBLJANA, SLOVENIA, 25–26 SEPTEMBER 2024

This report contributes to the ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and reflective learning process of the FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP), as outlined in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP). It documents the second CoP event, held in Slovenia, and builds directly upon the structure, methodologies, and feedback received from the inaugural CoP in Galway, Ireland. A final consolidated analysis of all four CoPs and the resulting measures will be compiled in Deliverable D4.2 – Report on CoP Networking Events (due M36, December 2025).

The FLIARA CoPs are not conferences, but dynamic, participatory learning spaces designed to foster collaboration, dialogue, and knowledge exchange between women innovators in rural areas, policymakers, researchers, and civil society actors. They are intentionally co-created and iterative, incorporating participant feedback and evolving with each edition.

In Slovenia, the hosting team deliberately followed successful practices implemented in Galway, including the Ambassador Innovation Journey roundtable, the Ambassadors' poster exhibition, and hands-on workshop sessions. These were thoughtfully expanded with additional elements: a field visit to innovative rural initiatives, a public exhibition, and creative hospitality touches such as locally crafted sweets and gifts in participants' welcome packages. Reflections from the first CoP informed specific enhancements. Lessons from Galway emphasized the value of small group interaction, targeted workshops, and a more balanced agenda, suggesting room for more networking, fewer repetitive elements, and opportunities to engage with local rural realities. These insights shaped the Slovenian CoP, which sought to offer both structure and spontaneity, policy dialogue and practice-based learning

Figure 32 Slovenia CoP participants after Day 1

As with all CoPs, the well-being and inclusion of FLIARA Ambassadors remained central. The Ethics Guardian attended the Slovenian event, continued monitoring this dimension, and produced a dedicated report, supported by anonymised ambassador and stakeholder feedback. This feedback was used to inform improvements for the following CoPs in Italy and Sweden.

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the Slovenian CoP: including the agenda, methodologies for participant selection, stakeholder composition, feedback processes, quantitative ratings, and qualitative feedback. It concludes with key takeaways and recommendations, contributing to the shared learning process that is at the core of the FLIARA CoP model.

COP EVENT 2: LJUBLJANA, 25-26 SEPTEMBER 2024

The second FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) Networking event happened in Ljubljana, Slovenia, on Wednesday September 25th and Thursday 26th of September 2024. Following a consortium-level decision based on insights from the first CoP in Galway, the Slovenian Community of Practice event was extended from the originally planned one day to a full two-day programme. This allowed for a deeper engagement with both policy and practice, more structured networking, and immersive learning opportunities. The event was hosted by the University of Ljubljana, whose team showed exceptional dedication in delivering a rich, high-quality experience. They successfully

secured additional funding from their institution, enabling the inclusion of high-level stakeholders - such as national and regional policymakers, decision-makers, and representatives from key rural and agricultural institutions—despite the limited CoP budget foreseen in the project.

Day 1 comprised of events in the Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana. Day 2 was a field trip entitled “Rural Slovenia and Woman-led Innovation”, to visit the projects of two Slovenian ambassadors and one Innovator. Also, on Day 0, there was a bonus event for participants arriving early, a city walking tour in English with a local tour guide.

A total of 81 participants registered for Day 1 of the Slovenian CoP, with 71 ultimately attending, according to the sign-in sheets. Among these were five local Slovenian stakeholders who joined on the day. For the Day 2 field visit, 82 people registered, but due to limited bus capacity, 42 participants were able to take part in the trip. Notably, all invited Ambassadors were able to attend: two from Czech Republic, two from Romania, one from Italy and two from Slovenia. Additionally, Slovenian 8 women innovators attended the event, building a large community of innovative women at the event. At least one representative of all Consortium project partners attended the event, with all ten countries being represented. Also participating were 43 stakeholders, mainly from Slovenia, providing an opportunity for a regional Eastern-Europe discussion on the FLIARA topics.

DESCRIPTION OF SLOVENIA COP ACTIVITIES

The event brought together female innovators, researchers, policy actors, and civil society participants in a participatory setting designed to strengthen cross-sector dialogue and contribute to ongoing policy learning within FLIARA. Building on effective practices piloted in Galway, such as the Ambassador Innovation Journey roundtable, the poster exhibition, and small group workshops, the Slovenian CoP introduced new features including a public exhibition, enhanced hospitality elements, and a field visit to rural innovation sites.

Figure 33 FLIARA Ambassador Innovation Journey. L-R: Iva Zdražilová & Alžběta Nagyová (Czechia), Sarah Khoudja (Italy), Patricia Marina Toma & Anca Veronica Marcu (Romania), Petra Matos & Saša Kržič (Slovenia), Moderator Petra Prešeren Golob

Objectives

The main objectives of the Slovenian CoP were to:

- Increase awareness of women's roles in rural innovation.
- Facilitate policy dialogue and cross-sector collaboration to strengthen support for women-led entrepreneurship.
- Create networking opportunities for sharing experiences and best practices among innovators, researchers, and policymakers.

Table 5 Slovenian CoP Agenda

FLIARA CoP Networking Event	
Day 0 – Tuesday September 25 th 2024	
Free City Tour, two hour guided tour in English, 4.00 – 6.00 pm	
Day 1 – Wednesday September 25 th 2024	
Launch of the FLIARA CoP, 9.00 am - 10.30 am	

- Welcome by Dr. Barbara Lampič (University of Ljubljana).
- Welcome by Dr. Maura Farrell, Project Coordinator (University of Galway)
- Welcome by Dr. Irena Semide, Associate Dean (University of Ljubljana)

-
- Dr. Maura Farrell (University of Galway): FLIARA Project Overview
 - Dr. Milica Antić Gaber (University of Ljubljana): What Are We Talking About When We Talk About Gender Equality?
 - Anton Jagodic (Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia): Integration and Cooperation in Slovenian Rural Areas.
 - Dr. Irma Potočnik Slavič (University of Ljubljana): The Potential of LEADER/CLLD in Slovenia: The (In)Visible Role of Women in Rural Development.
 - Dr. Štefan Bojnec (University of Primorska): How to Support Innovations and Women Entrepreneurship in Rural Areas?

Ambassador Innovation Journey, 11.00 am - 12.30 pm

- Moderator: Petra Prešeren Golob

7 FLIARA Ambassadors:

- Petra Matos and Saša Kržič from Slovenia
- Anca Veronica Marcu and Patricia Marina Toma from Romania
- Sarah Khoudja from Italy
- Iva Zdražilová and Alžběta Nagyová from Czech Republic.

Lunch break, 12.30 pm - 1.30 pm

Results from FLIARA project 1.30 pm - 2.00 pm

Workshop 1: 2.00 pm - 3.20 pm

- Using Future Visions to Build Policy Supporting Women-led Innovation.

Two parallel group sessions, 3.45 pm - 5.05 pm

- Workshop 2: Empowering Women to Lead: Shaping Policy for Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas.
- Workshop 3: Policy Practice Discussions.

Feedback from the Workshops and Wrap Up, 5.05 - 5.45 pm

Dinner, 6.15 - 9.00 pm

Day 2 – Thursday September 26th, 2024: Full Day on the Field: Rural Slovenia and Women-led Innovation

1st stop – Borovnica, 8.30 am - 10.30 am

- Ambassador Innovation Journey by **Ms Saša Kržič, Mikrozelenje Šebenik**.
- Discussion with representatives from the **LAG “Barje z zaledjem”** and innovative bee-keeper Ms Malči Božnar.

2nd stop – Kastelec, 11.30 am - 1.15 pm

- Ambassador Innovation Journey by **Ms Petra Matos, Park Istra**.
- Discussion with different actors who are working with Petra (Center for Social Work “Južna Primorska”, **Ms Dijana Plješa**).

3rd stop – Seča, 2.30 pm - 4.30 pm

- Woman-led Innovation Journey by **Ms Nina Froggatt, Gramona**.
- Walk around the family farm, concluded with a tasting session Invited stakeholders for discussion

Key Sessions (Day 1)

The first day of the CoP began with a series of thematic presentations by leading academics and practitioners, offering diverse perspectives on gender equality, innovation, and rural development.

Dr. Barbara Lampič (University of Ljubljana) opened the event by highlighting the importance of rural innovation and the role of academia in supporting transformative change. Dr. Maura Farrell (University of Galway) provided an overview of the FLIARA project's aims and methodology, situating it within broader efforts to support sustainable, women-led innovation in rural Europe. Dr. Milica Antić Gaber (University of Ljubljana) delivered a powerful keynote, *What Are We Talking About When We Talk About Gender Equality?*, unpacking the structural barriers that rural women face.

Additional contributions included a presentation from the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia on the role of women's associations in empowering rural entrepreneurship; Dr. Irma Potočnik Slavič's (University of Ljubljana) analysis of the LEADER/CLLD programme and the (in)visible role of women in these policy frameworks; and Dr. Štefan Bojnec (University of Primorska) on aligning EU and national innovation policies to better support women entrepreneurs.

Interactive Session

To further encourage participant engagement, an interactive session invited attendees to reflect on innovation and the future of the FLIARA project. Two guiding questions structured the exercise:

- What unconventional or radical idea could spark a wave of innovation among rural women?
- What must we not forget in the FLIARA project, and how can we ensure the results lead to impact in practice?

Participants contributed written reflections on post-it notes, which were collected on thematic boards in the main room. This engagement was also extended beyond the physical event through a LinkedIn post, continuing the dialogue with the wider FLIARA network.

Field Visit

The second day of the CoP was dedicated to a field visit, directly responding to feedback from Galway participants who had requested more tangible, place-based learning experiences. The visit introduced attendees to three innovative women-led initiatives in rural Slovenia:

- **Mikrozelenje Šebenik** – Saša Kržič shared her approach to microgreens production, focusing on sustainability and community connection.
- **Park Istra** – Petra Matos presented this volunteer-based rural development project, highlighting practices of inclusion and community-building.

- **Gramona Family Farm** – Nina Froggatt reflected on integrating local food production with sustainability and economic resilience.

These visits helped translate policy dialogue and project objectives into grounded, real-world examples of women shaping the future of rural Europe.

Workshop Descriptions

Guided by the GA the SAP outlines that one of the two main purposes of The FLIARA CoP is to develop an interchange platform for multi-actor exchanges, via a series of four EU workshops with all relevant key stakeholders. The SAP outlines how Workshops are a key part of the FLIARA conceptual framework to “explore policy benchmarking, participatory scenario development for policy and broader policy dialogues. This will allow the exploration of the hypothesis and leverage point “Transforming policy and governance towards gender equality” and how “Governance solutions can provide opportunities, incentives, and support for female innovators”. In addition, by FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors and other women leading innovations in agriculture and rural areas being at the centre of the FLIARA CoP Network this also links to leverage point “Women in Decision-Making” and supports “Increasing women’s opportunities to participate in decisions concerning their lives”.

Continuing on from the Galway CoP event, 3 workshops were included in the Slovenian event, that feed into three different tasks in 2 different work packages, these tasks build on and feed into wider work packages in the following way, as outlined in the GA:

Table 6 FLIARA CoP Task descriptions Slovenia

Work package WP4 – FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Task 4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design
Task 4.3 will continue the work on benchmarking EU and National Policy and Legal Frameworks by assessing the work carried out in WP1 and the results of case studies from WP3 and devising a strategy to engage participants at the four Community of Practice Networking events via focus groups and workshops to discuss the findings and ascertain key issues to be brought forward to the policy design and assessment workshops. These focus groups/workshops will be held alongside the Community of Practice Networking events. This task will also play a role in organising participatory scenario building exercises, which will be finalised in WP5.
Work package WP5 – Policy Design and Assessment
TASK 5.2: Policy practice discussions
This task will embrace a multi-actor approach through a policy practice dialogue taking place at the four Community of Practice Networking events (WP4). The purpose is to break down disciplinary silos and engage users and experts in exploring lessons learned and outcomes, policy, institutional and other challenges encountered across FLIARA. Exploring this in four regional settings ensures that diverse regional contexts will also be observed. The outcome of this task will ensure a more end-user effective policy, in addition to informing recommendations for structural changes of governance frameworks at different levels and informing national policy environments.

TASK 5.3: Develop new policy proposals

Conduct a series of focus groups with key stakeholders, namely women leading farming and rural innovations, policymakers and other relevant stakeholders in a process of Participatory Scenario Development. The qualitative and participatory techniques applied in a Participatory Scenario Development exercise encourage discussion, deliberation, and the exchange of thoughts. The process also provides a framework to support future decisions and stimulate engagement in the process of change. The University of Galway and TU Delft will lead on the Participatory Scenario Development, with participation from other partners.

Following the steps outlined in the SAP, each of the workshop leads added objectives for the workshop in the “FLIARA CoP Task Content Builder” and in the lead -up to the event, they collaborated with the host to consolidate a list of guests which included all types of relevant stakeholders, connecting FLIARA Ambassadors, policy makers, LAG representatives, civil society/non-governmental organization representatives, researchers, media and the Consortium (including the FLIARA SAB). The timing format used in Galway was maintained, with Task 5.3 happening on its own (in 2 rooms) and tasks T4.3 & T5.2 happen simultaneously in two different rooms. Workshop leads defined themes and needs (how many tables, what group size, what extra resources needed), with the following descriptions being shared in the Linktree, to describe the workshops in a more appealing way.

Table 7 Workshops descriptions Slovenia

(Workshop 1) T5.3: Develop new policy proposals/ Scenario Development
Workshop Title: Using future visions to build policy supporting women-led innovation
This workshop involves participants discussing future visions for farming and rural areas. The goal is to focus on the visions participants feel women could make an important contribution to and identify the policy actions needed to make these future visions a reality. Developed from the FLIARA future foresight research, a wide range of visions impacting rural areas and farming can be chosen for discussion. This includes topics such as local food and sustainable lifestyles. Participants will take away new ideas for potential future policy.
(Workshop 2 - Focus Group) T4.3: Benchmarking and Policy Design
Workshop Title: Empowering Women to Lead: Shaping Policy for Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
The objectives of this activity are twofold: (a) verify the data already collected within the project in relation to public policies and laws which frame rural women’s innovations, and (b) to create a supportive community for women innovators to connect, share experiences, and foster collaboration with various types of stakeholders including policy/decision-makers, Local actions group/LEADER and researchers.
(Workshop 3) T5.2: Policy practice discussions
Workshop Title: Policy practice discussion
This workshop aims to identify gaps and ideas to strengthen current policies on female-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas based on lived experiences of female farmers and entrepreneurs. Mixed groups of participants (6-9 persons) share their experiences, insights, and opinions on the challenges they faced during their innovation journey with their workaround or solutions. The discussion was based on the four main themes of the FLIARA

project. The second step in this workshop was to translate these problems and solutions into changes to be made in policy issues from local to European levels.

Communication Roadmap

As with the first Community of Practice in Galway, participant outreach and registration for the Slovenian CoP followed a coordinated communication strategy led by the host team in collaboration with CE, WP4 Lead (ECOLISE), and the Project Coordinator & host of the 1st CoP Even (Galway). Email invitation lists were developed using a combination of FLIARA consortium partner contacts, national networks, and targeted outreach to key stakeholder groups. These included local and national policymakers, rural development practitioners, women innovators, academics, and civil society organisations. The registration process was managed online, with forms for the main event and the field trip, allowing the organisers to monitor and adjust logistics accordingly. Final attendance included 71 participants on Day 1 and 42 on Day 2, reflecting strong engagement across the two-day programme.

A dedicated Linktree was embedded on the FLIARA website to centralise access to all relevant resources, including the agenda, travel guide, workshop descriptions, and background materials. Event updates were also shared via FLIARA's communication channels, supporting wider visibility.

At the entrance of the venue, a communication board invited participants to respond to three key questions about innovation, visibility, and the legacy of FLIARA. Questions were posted in both English and Slovenian, with responses collected via post-it notes to encourage informal, multilingual reflection. This participatory tool—newly introduced in Slovenia—fostered real-time engagement and inspired deeper consideration of project themes.

The poster section of all 20 FLIARA Ambassadors was on display in the entrance hall, providing visibility to the broader European network. On the second floor, the Slovenian team curated a detailed exhibition of national FLIARA results, showcasing the contributions of interviewed women from across the country. Many of these women played a direct role in the CoP: one was the main caterer, another baked traditional sweets, several contributed to the goodie bags with handcrafted items, and others presented publications or products as part of the exhibition.

Following the successful example from Galway, a bilingual FLIARA booklet (Slovenian English) was produced (both online and print format) and distributed at the event. It featured profiles of Slovenian innovators identified through FLIARA field research, celebrating their achievements and making their stories accessible to a wider audience.

Overall, the communication roadmap successfully combined strategic outreach, practical coordination, and creative engagement. It ensured the event was inclusive, participatory, and aligned with the CoP's broader goal of amplifying the voices and visibility of rural women innovators.

Table 8 Slovenian CoP questions for interaction with the participants

1. New, unconventional ideas
What unconventional or radical idea could spark a wave of innovation among rural women?
2. Not forget / Efficiency in practice
What must we not forget or overlook in the FLIARA project?
3. Promoting results
How should we promote the FLIARA project results to ensure their effective implementation in practice?

FIELD VISIT SUMMARY

Figure 34 FLIARA Field Trip to Rural Slovenia: Ljubljana, Borovnica, Kastelec, Seča

As part of the Slovenian CoP, a full-day field trip was organised to enable participants to engage directly with women-led rural innovations and relevant stakeholders. This visit supported the dual purpose of the FLIARA CoP Network: to enable multi-actor knowledge exchange and strengthen visibility for rural women innovators identified through WP3.

The first stop was in Borovnica, where participants met with representatives from the local LAG “Barje z Zaledjem.” This session facilitated dialogue between CoP attendees,

LAG staff, and Slovenian policy representatives on regional development strategies and challenges specific to supporting women’s innovation. Nearby, participants visited the production site of Saša Kržič, a FLIARA Ambassador and founder of Mikrozelenje Šebenik. Her microgreens business sparked discussion around sustainable production, business adaptation during COVID-19, and direct-to-consumer innovation through home-growing kits.

The second stop was Park Istra, led by Ambassador Petra Matos, a community-based volunteer initiative for rural revitalisation. Joined by social workers, the group explored how socially inclusive practices can address rural marginalisation. Participants shared experiences around governance models, community impact, and project sustainability.

The final visit was to Gramona Family Farm in Seča, run by Nina Froggatt, focusing on regenerative agriculture and eco-tourism. The group toured olive groves, discussed climate adaptation strategies, and concluded with an olive oil tasting.

This immersive trip highlighted Slovenia’s diverse rural landscape, fostered informal networking, and offered grounded insights into innovation, resilience, and cross-sector collaboration.

FEEDBACK FROM THE SLOVENIAN COP

In response to the Slovenian CoP host's request to streamline the evaluation process, a more concise set of feedback surveys was developed. While the core questions followed the structure outlined in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP), their order was adapted for greater clarity and usability. For this CoP, Mentimeter was selected as the primary tool for collecting feedback, replacing Google Forms used in the Galway event. The decision was based on Mentimeter’s more visually engaging interface and ease of use for participants.

Separate surveys were designed for each day of the event and tailored to two distinct groups: FLIARA Ambassadors and general stakeholders. Participants were invited to complete the surveys via QR codes displayed at the end of each day, with follow-up reminders sent by email to maximise response rates.

To respect participants’ time and encourage completion, the number of questions was intentionally reduced while still capturing key areas of evaluation, including satisfaction with organisation, content, inclusivity, and impact. This adapted approach ensured a more efficient yet effective method of gathering meaningful feedback from all attendees.

Table 9 Registered Stakeholders & Feedback for both Slovenia CoP days

Type	Number	Participated in Workshops	Feedback Day 1	Feedback Day 2
Ambassadors	7		15 (see note)	6
Innovators	8		3	3

Consortium Partners	30		24	16
SAB	0		0	0
Stakeholders	43		11	4
Total	78		53	29

Table 10 Stakeholder responses, Days 1 & 2 Slovenia CoP

	Day 1		Day 2	
Stakeholder type	Responses	Group %	Responses	Group %
Consortium Member	24	65	16	73
Policy or Decision Maker	0	0	0	0
Researcher	3	8	2	9
LAG member	4	11	1	5
Journalist	0	0	0	0
Activist	3	8	0	0
Woman Innovator	3	8	3	14
Total	38	100%	23	100%

Feedback questions and scoring

There were 7 questions in total – the first 4 questions were all sliding scale answers, ranging from 1 to 5 (1 = unsatisfactory / 5 = excellent: 1 = No likely positive impact / 5 = Large likely positive impact) for quick click responses on several points. The last 3 questions provided a space for longer feedback in written form from the participants, they explored 3 questions relating to each day of the FLIARA CoP, including:

- What are your final takeaways...
- What improvements do you see possible for similar future events...
- Any additional thoughts or comments regarding the event...

FEEDBACK FROM AMBASSADORS

The overall satisfaction of the FLIARA Ambassadors who attended the Slovenian CoP was notably high. Day 1 received an average score of 4.7, while Day 2 was rated a perfect 5.0 by Ambassadors – an exceptional result reflecting the quality and relevance of the event, and particularly the effort and dedication of the Slovenian partner and host. Ambassadors particularly valued the opportunity to connect with one another, meet consortium members, and visit local innovation projects during the field trip, which was consistently highlighted as the most impactful element.

Despite these strong evaluations, several constructive suggestions were made. Ambassadors felt that the Day 1 agenda was overly condensed, limiting time for informal exchanges. There were repeated calls for more dedicated sessions exclusively for Ambassadors and local innovators, particularly following the Ambassador Innovation Journey, to deepen discussions and address complex themes.

Aesthetic and spatial aspects were also raised, some suggested hosting the Ambassador Journey in a more inviting, celebratory setting rather than a formal lecture hall. Importantly, the FLIARA Ambassadors noted a desire to move beyond polished presentations to build trust and openly explore challenging topics such as financial independence. Suggestions included practical workshops on funding opportunities and arranging shared accommodation to encourage informal networking. Finally, several Ambassadors expressed a wish for greater engagement from high-level policymakers during the field visit.

AMBASSADOR EXPERIENCE AND ETHICS OVERVIEW

The Ethics Guardian assessed the participation of the Ambassadors during the Slovenian CoP as highly successful. On Day 1, Ambassadors were prominently included across the full programme, including evening social activities. On Day 2, several Slovenian Ambassadors actively guided the field visits, offering in-depth insights into their innovation journeys. The overall time and space allocated to Ambassadors was deemed sufficient.

The Ambassador's engagement throughout all workshops and sessions was notably high. Each had the opportunity to contribute perspectives and share practical examples, which enriched discussions and supported the co-creation of recommendations. Their enthusiasm to participate in and contribute to the FLIARA Community remained consistent with their involvement in the first CoP in Galway.

The Ethics Guardian observed that Ambassadors felt fully comfortable and supported throughout the event. Czech participants expressed appreciation for the inclusive and respectful environment, which bolstered their confidence despite language concerns. The event facilitated both personal and professional exchanges, with new connections and future collaboration opportunities emerging.

Overall, the Ambassadors were energized, active, and fully integrated into the event. The atmosphere was described as warm, welcoming, and intellectually stimulating, with all elements—from content to catering—receiving very positive feedback.

STAKEHOLDER FEEDBACK

Stakeholders expressed a high level of satisfaction with the Slovenian CoP, with Day 1 rated at 4.6 and Day 2 at 4.7. Key highlights included the Ambassador Innovation Journey, which allowed participants to connect with the women's personal stories, and

the field visit, which provided direct insight into the impact of women-led innovations in rural communities. Many stakeholders emphasised the authenticity and originality of the projects and the valuable social contribution of the ambassadors, with Park Istra specifically noted as a standout example of community-driven innovation.

Despite the overall positive feedback, several areas for improvement were identified. Stakeholders felt the agenda was too full, limiting informal networking opportunities. There were repeated suggestions to reduce lecture-based sessions in favour of more participatory formats such as roundtables. Greater visibility and engagement for ambassadors within the programme was also recommended, along with a more immersive setting, moving away from auditorium-style rooms to more inclusive and circular arrangements.

Recommendations also pointed to longer-term impact: increasing media visibility through alignment with public events, enhancing policymaker participation in rural venues, and strengthening online engagement through platforms like LinkedIn. Finally, while the inclusion of women-led catering was appreciated, stakeholders highlighted the need for adequate food and refreshments and suggested adding a social dinner to foster deeper connections.

FEEDBACK FROM TASK LEADERS

Task Reflection 4.3

The T4.3 workshop in Ljubljana built directly on the experience and lessons learned from the first CoP event held in Galway. In Galway, the focus group methodology proved effective in encouraging multi-actor exchanges, but challenges were identified around the need for clearer facilitation, better distribution of stakeholder types at tables, and more intentional workshop design aligned with policy development objectives.

Overall, T4.3 workshop at the Slovenian CoP successfully met its objectives, enabling meaningful engagement between women innovators, researchers, and rural development stakeholders. Despite last-minute adjustments in group composition, the format of four mixed tables facilitated productive dialogue. Ambassadors contributed actively, sharing their experiences and policy perspectives.

Well-prepared facilitation teams, supported by a clear Focus Group Guide and follow-up questions, ensured inclusive and flowing discussions. Each table summarised key takeaways, later shared in the plenary session, supporting mutual learning across groups.

Content was co-created in alignment with WP1 and WP5, with an additional question added to explore participants' policy wishes. This informed a new focus on actionable recommendations and further examination of LAGs and LEADER programmes.

Lessons included the importance of having committed workshop participants, improved room acoustics, and gender-balanced facilitation teams. While the workshop in Ljubljana

maintained the core structure of the Galway format, the refinements applied according to the feedback received resulted in more focused, inclusive, and policy-relevant conversations. Recommendations for future CoPs include running workshops sequentially (not in parallel), enhancing spatial arrangements to reduce noise, and evolving the format toward more participatory policy design exercises in line with T4.3 objectives.

Task Reflection 5.2

The Task 5.2 policy workshop in Slovenia built on the experience of the first FLIARA CoP in Galway, implementing several key improvements based on prior feedback. These included clearer instructions at the outset, assigning each table an initial discussion topic (female, innovation, rural entrepreneurship, or agriculture), and shifting the focus from problems to practical, solution-oriented outcomes. Unlike in Galway, possibilities for local policy were intentionally excluded to streamline dialogue.

These adjustments led to more structured conversations and direct and diverse answers, with facilitators being better prepared to guide discussions without dominating them. The workshop setup—mixed tables including innovators and policy advisors, fostered inclusive exchanges and co-creation of content. Discussions varied in scope but included a notable shift toward European-level policy reflections.

Key recommendations for future CoPs include maintaining a clearer thematic focus, equipping facilitators with strong introductory guidance, and exploring under-addressed contextual factors, such as the influence of regional histories on innovation and empowerment narratives.

The single room setting was effective, though ensuring an even distribution of stakeholder types across tables remains a priority. Overall, the improvements made in Slovenia significantly enhanced the quality and focus of the T5.2 workshop, providing a solid model for replication and refinement in upcoming FLIARA events.

Task Reflection 5.3

Task 5.3: Participatory Visioning Workshop in Slovenia built on the first implementation in Galway, refining the format to strengthen policy-oriented outcomes. Based on lessons from the first CoP, the workshop introduced elaboration groups that expanded on the vision card discussions and supported the development of concrete policy suggestions to foster women's entrepreneurship.

One of the key insights from Slovenia was the marked difference in vision card selections compared to Galway, reflecting national contexts and priorities. The Slovenian workshop highlighted the need to tailor engagement to local realities while ensuring alignment with FLIARA's broader policy aims.

Co-creation was central to the process. The University of Turku and the University of Galway co-designed the sessions, which involved ten vision groups and three elaboration groups. Tools such as vision cards, printed materials, and visual table arrangements helped facilitate structured discussion across multiple rooms.

Recommendations for future CoPs include improving coordination across facilitators and rooms to ensure consistent instructions and flow. The scenario-building process will continue in future CoPs by developing scenario cards based on the most popular visions from Slovenia. Overall, the refined format significantly improved participatory depth and policy relevance.

FEEDBACK FROM COMMUNICATION

As outlined in the Strategic Action Plan and reported by WP6 lead partner CE, Task 6.2 focuses on the FLIARA “Campaign of Visibility,” which aims to showcase Ambassador innovation journeys through audiovisual content, including photos, videos, and podcasts. These materials will contribute to the FLIARA video blog and feed into T4.4, the development of the FLIARA Toolkit.

In Slovenia, although the hosts provided a space for video interviews, no dedicated time slot was allocated in the agenda, unlike in Galway. This limited WP6’s ability to record content without disrupting other CoP activities or Ambassador participation. CE recommends designating a parallel session for recordings in future events, allowing the Campaign of Visibility to proceed without interfering with the main programme.

Progress has been made in refining the methodology for the Ambassador Innovation Journey activity as main activity in the event agenda: interview questions were sent in advance to hosts and Ambassador’s buddies, translated into local languages, and discussed during a preparatory session with the moderator of the Ambassador Innovation Journey activity.

Additional recommendations include incorporating a dedicated an exclusive networking slot for Ambassadors and promoting use of the LinkedIn space (FLIARA LinkedIn Group) throughout the event. CE also suggests regular reminders about the Linktree and encouraging moderators to reference it during sessions to support networking continuity.

LESSONS LEARNED AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Slovenian Community of Practice (CoP) event received overall high satisfaction ratings, with most scores ranging between 4 and 5 on the Mentimeter platform. The Ambassador Journey on Day 1 and the Field Trip on Day 2 were consistently identified as key highlights. While the structure of the agenda: consolidating formal activities into a single day to allow a full field visit on Day 2 was generally appreciated, several challenges related to pacing and engagement emerged.

KEY STRENGTHS

Ambassador Journey

The Ambassador Journey offered a powerful platform for ambassadors to share their personal stories, motivations, and challenges. Moderated with sensitivity and insight, the session was praised for its emotional depth and relevance. However, several stakeholders suggested that more time and a more visually engaging setting, such as a space outside the main lecture hall, could enhance the impact.

Field Visit

The field trip was a clear highlight, offering direct insight into the realities of women-led rural innovations. Participants valued the opportunity to observe projects firsthand, interact with Ambassadors in their working environments, and engage in informal networking during bus travel. The added contextual commentary about regional history and socio-economic conditions further enriched the experience.

Workshops

The workshops demonstrated strong engagement, supported by effective facilitation and a shift in focus from problem identification to solution-building. Ambassadors, LAG representatives, and researchers contributed meaningfully. The structure, refined based on feedback from the Galway CoP, improved co-creation outcomes. However, future iterations should encourage higher retention of policy-level stakeholders throughout the afternoon sessions.

AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

1. Networking Opportunities

A consistent recommendation across feedback was to increase dedicated time for networking and peer exchange. The tightly packed agenda on Day 1 limited informal interactions. A structured networking session at the beginning or during midday could allow stakeholders, ambassadors, and local innovators more time to connect. The use of communication tools—such as a physical comment board or the online LinkedIn space—could be expanded and better promoted.

2. Visibility Campaign Recording (WP6)

WP6 activities, particularly the Campaign of Visibility video recordings, were constrained by the lack of a dedicated time slot on the agenda. Unlike Galway, this limited the involvement of both the WP6 leader and ambassadors. Going forward, a parallel or separate recording session should be included to avoid scheduling conflicts. CE has refined the methodology: questions are shared in advance, translated for the ambassadors, and discussed during preparatory sessions with the Innovation Journey moderator.

3. Deeper Ambassador Engagement

Participants, including ambassadors themselves, expressed the need for more intimate

and trust-based spaces. While public presentations are valuable, they may unintentionally encourage polished narratives rather than fostering vulnerability and collective reflection. Topics such as financial independence—described as “the elephant in the room”—require closed, ambassador-only sessions for meaningful exploration. Suggestions included shared accommodation, informal meals, or a private session after the Ambassador Journey. These spaces could also inform future online CoP sessions with targeted, sensitive discussions.

LOGISTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Overall, the venue and logistical arrangements were suitable. The second floor hosted exhibitions, and the entrance hall featured the full poster display of all 20 FLIARA ambassadors. Food and refreshments—largely prepared by local innovators—were highly appreciated and contributed to the inclusive, community-driven tone of the event. Nonetheless, formalising the provision of meals and adding a social dinner may further support informal networking and knowledge exchange.

The Slovenian CoP reflected the strength of FLIARA’s evolving participatory design and relevance of Strategic Action Plan (D4.1), as well as the dedication to co-creation of all the partners involved, particularly the host, University of Ljubljana. Drawing on feedback and improvements implemented after Galway, it succeeded in amplifying Ambassador voices, strengthening multi-actor collaboration, and enhancing place-based learning and macro-regional contextualization. The recommendations outlined here will support the continued refinement of future CoPs, particularly in Italy and Sweden.

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE EVENT

FLIARA event report

- FLIARA’s 2nd Community of Practice Event Brings Women-Led Innovation to the Forefront in Slovenia: <https://fliara.eu/fliaras-2nd-community-of-practice-event-brings-women-led-innovation-to-the-forefront-in-slovenia/>

VIDEO:

- FLIARA Community of Practice (Ljubljana, Slovenia) - 25th September 2024 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hJyUbU9MW2U>

2nd FLIARA Online CoP Event information on the FLIARA website:

- FLIARA Linktree <https://fliara.eu/fliara-slovenia-cop/>
- FLIARA Booklet - Slovenian Innovations <https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Booklet-FLIARA-Slovenia.pdf>

Factsheets of the women innovators visited on Field Trip, on Sept 25:

- Slovenian Ambassador Saša Kržič, Mikrozelenje Šebenik: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/sasa-krzic/>

- Slovenian Ambassador Petra Matos, Park Istra: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/petra-matos/>
- Slovenian Innovator Nina Froggatt, Kmetija Gramona: <https://fliara.eu/innovator/nina-froggatt/>

Public LinkedIn posts:

- Maura Farrell: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/maurafarrell_horizoneurope-innovativewomen-activity-7245522521062543360-z5H6
- Tara Farrell, CEO at Longford Women's Link (Consortium Partner, Ireland)
 - Day 1: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/teefarrell_communityofpractice-ruralinnovation-femaleentrepreneurs-activity-7244639612738891776-7toO & https://www.linkedin.com/posts/teefarrell_communityofpractice-ruralinnovation-femaleentrepreneurship-activity-7244676283849150465-6oCK
 - Day 2: Field Trip: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/teefarrell_innovation-womeninbusiness-femaleentrepreneurship-activity-7245086895594967041-34UU
- Anne Kinsella, Teagasc (Consortium Partner, Ireland): https://www.linkedin.com/posts/anne-kinsella-bba02719_fliara-rural-innovation-activity-7245493538145144832-BHT-

Other FLIARA resources

- FLIARA - Community of Practice, digital space on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9833161/>

Local coverage of the Slovenia CoP:

- **Print media**

Agricultural (national) journal "*Kmečki glas*", 09/10/2024, article with a title Agricultural journal "*Pot utirajo prodorne posameznice*" / Trailblazing women are paving the way.

- **Online**

Agricultural journal "*Kmečki glas*" published also online (11/10/2024): [Pot utirajo prodorne posameznice | Kmečki Glas](#)

DRSP/Slovenian Rural Development Network online newsletter: [Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja - Mednarodno srečanje izkustvene skupnosti projekta FLIARA, ki se osredotoča na inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju](#)

- **Academic**

Article in journal DELA, Dec 2024. Authors: Barbara Lampič, Sara Mikolič, Irma Potočnik Slavič, Lea Rebernik. Title: PROJEKT FLIARA: TRAJNOSTNI RAZVOJ PODEŽELJA, NOVI PRISTOPI, VLOGA IN MOČ ŽENSK / FLIARA Project: Sustainable Rural Development, New Approaches, Role and Empowerment of Women, pp. 180-185. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4312/dela.62.157-185>

ANNEX 3 – EVENT REPORT: 3RD FLIARA COP NETWORKING EVENT – RENDE, ITALY, 29–30 JANUARY 2025

This report is to assist in the monitoring, evaluation and reflection of the FLIARA CoP, as laid out in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP). A final summary of these results and measures taken due to them will be included in deliverable D4.2 Report on CoP Networking events, which will be delivered by December 2025 (M36).

The ambassadors' wellbeing was monitored throughout the implementation of the Italian CoP. The FLIARA ethics Guardian uses their role throughout the activities to observe, monitor and support the well-being of the Ambassadors. For the purposes of this element of the project and for ease of identification for the Women Ambassadors, the title of FLIARA CoP Ethics Guardian has been developed. The Ethics Guardian participated in the Italian CoP event and wrote a report, which is supported by feedback from the ambassadors themselves and other stakeholders that participated.

The report prepared by the Ethics Guardian after the Italian CoP event was analysed to allow for adjustments and improvements for the following and final networking event in Sweden. An analysis of the 4 reports and measures taken after each of them will be compiled within the final report. All feedback received by the Ethics Guardian during the FLIARA CoP was anonymised, analysed and compiled to be included in the deliverable D4.2 Report on CoP Networking events.

IMPROVEMENTS IMPLEMENTED FOLLOWING THE 2ND FLIARA COP EVENT IN SLOVENIA

Networking: following the feedback received after the event in Slovenia, a dedicated networking activity was added for the Ambassadors (Networking Aperitif – Day 1). The activity was open to include all participants during the Networking Dinner (Day 1).

Video Recording: while a dedicated slot for interviewing the Ambassadors was not allocated in the event agenda, the way this activity was organized led it its success. Namely, prior preparation (sending the questions beforehand to the Ambassadors), having a dedicated room during Day 1, and a natural background during Day 2, as well as sufficient time (during coffee breaks, lunch time, etc.) allowed for all interviews with the Ambassadors to be conducted effectively. Additionally, following a suggestion from FLIARA project Coordinators, interviews with the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) members present were also conducted successfully.

Ambassador's Needs: the need for dedicated, trust-building moments—such as private discussions, shared meals, and field visits—to foster deeper connections and address challenging topics like financial independence was expressed following the CoP event in Slovenia. This was taken into consideration when designing the agenda for the event, with the hosts maintaining close contact with the participating Ambassadors. Furthermore, one Ambassador from Italy directly collaborated with the host in order to design the networking activity for the Ambassadors. Furthermore, feedback from Ambassadors participating in a second FLIARA CoP Networking Event revealed that

recurrent in-person presence at these events considerably builds trust, fosters self-confidence and overall forges the deeper connections among them which the FLIARA CoP is aiming for. The evolution of the interpersonal relationships between the FLIARA Ambassadors materialized during the Italian CoP into the creation of a closed WhatsApp group which includes 13 Ambassadors at the moment (with the rest being invited to join shortly).

COP EVENT 3: RENDE (CALABRIA), 29-30 JANUARY 2025

The third FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) Networking event took place in Rende, Italy, on Wednesday, the 29th, and Thursday, the 30th of January 2025. The public event was followed on the 31st by an internal meeting of the Consortium Partners, which focused on D5.1 Policy Booklet and Policy Briefs. Day 1 comprised of events in the Congress Centre of the University of Calabria. Day 2 was dedicated to a trip in the region to visit the projects of 2 women innovators and have a discussion with LAG operators in the Valle del Crati area, as well as the virtual tours of the initiatives of the two Italian Ambassadors, followed by discussions.

The total number of registered participants, for the whole duration of the event, was 73. Additionally, 9 Italian participants (mainly UNICAL researchers and Italian stakeholders) and 1 SAB (replacement) member registered on Day 1 directly at the event venue and signed the attendance sheet. Out of the originally registered participants, 11 were unable to attend. The participants on day 1 were 72. 52 of the participants travelled for the field visit on Day 2.

Figure 35 Italy CoP participants during the field trip (day 2, 30th of January 25).

DESCRIPTION OF ITALIAN COP ACTIVITIES

Day 1 activities took place at the Congress Centre of the University of Calabria from 9 to 17:45 and were continued with networking events at different venues. After the opening of the Italian FLIARA CoP Event, a FLIARA project and results overview was presented by the Consortium partners. An Italian perspective on agriculture, innovation and women was given by the Italian CAP Rural Network representatives, complemented by a round table on the topic of Women and Innovation in rural areas which focused on the case of the Calabria region with local stakeholders. The Ambassador Innovation Journey roundtable discussion with Sarah Khoudja (Italy), Sofia De Matteis (Italy), Saša Kržič (Slovenia), Ursula Kelly (Ireland), Natalia Díaz (Spain), Malin Axelsson (Sweden) ended the morning activities.

The second part of Day 1 began with Workshop 1 (T5.3): Using Future Visions to Build Policy Supporting Women-led Innovation and continued with the parallel activities Workshop 2: Empowering Women to Lead: Shaping Policy for Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas (T4.3), and respectively Workshop 3: Policy Practice Discussions (T5.2). The activities at the Congress Centre were concluded after a short feedback session on the workshops, and from FLIARA SAB. The networking activities outside UNICAL continued with the Networking Aperitif for Ambassadors, and a networking dinner for all participants.

Day 2 was dedicated to field visits and virtual tours of various women-led innovation in Italy. The first project visited was that of Rosaria Amalia Capparelli, the mayor of San Benedetto Ullano and the operators of the Reception and Integration System (SAI)'s project "Insieme a San Benedetto Ullano" ("Together with San Benedetto Ullano"), followed by a visit to the Serragiumenta Farm in Altomonte, led by Rita Bilotti. Although initially included in the program, the visit to La Tatina farm in San Martino di Finita had to be cancelled due to unforeseen circumstances which prevented the host from receiving the group visit. In the afternoon, virtual tours consisting of two videos took place in Serragiumenta. The viewing of the videos with women innovators from the south-eastern coast of Calabria and Cilento was followed by a debate with the FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors in Italy, Sofia De Matteis and Sarah Khoudja, together with women innovators from the associations We're South and Circe. Representatives from the LAG Valle del Crati joined the event in Serragiumenta, sharing insights into local projects and explaining how innovative women were involved and supported through LEADER/CLLD.

The visits and virtual tours focused on unveiling the innovation journeys of the women leading them, and highlighting the importance of networking, collective action and mutual support.

Table 11 Italian CoP Agenda

FLIARA CoP Networking Event
Day 1 – Wednesday January 29th 2025
<p>Launch of the FLIARA CoP, 9:00 – 11:00</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome by Ercole Giap Parini, Director of the Social and Political Science Department (University of Calabria). • Welcome by Giovanna Vingelli, Rector's Delegate on Gender Equality (University of Calabria). • Welcome by Silvia Sivini, FLIARA Italian Research Team Coordinator (University of Calabria). • FLIARA Project Overview - Maura Farrell, Project Coordinator (University of Galway). • Agriculture, innovation, women: an Italian perspective - Catia Zumpano, Barbara Forcina, Grazia Valentino (Italian CAP RURAL Network). • Results from FLIARA project: • The FLIARA Framework: Insights for Future Rural and Farm Policy. Louise Weir, Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh. • Empowering Women for Rural Sustainability: Insights from FLIARA's Foresight and Trend Analysis. Tuomas Kuhmonen, Beyla Tembo. • Empowering Female-Led Innovations in Rural Europe: Insights from FLIARA's Case Studies. Silvia Sivini, Annie Roos. • Round table. Women and Innovation in rural areas: the case of Calabria Region - Giovanna Vingelli (Moderator), Guido Mignolli – LAG Terre Locridee, Marina Smurra – Confagricoltura Donne, Rosaria Talarico – CIA Donne in Campo, Maria Grazia Barone- Associazione Nazionale Donne dell'Olio Aps, Stefania Fratto - Associazione Donne e Diritti. <p>Coffee break, 11:00 – 11:30</p> <p>Ambassador Innovation Journey, 11:30 – 13:00</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderator: Irene Leonardelli <p>6 FLIARA Ambassadors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sarah Khoudja from Italy • Sofia De Matteis from Italy; • Saša Kržič from Slovenia; • Ursula Kelly from Ireland; • Natalia Díaz from Spain; • Malin Axelsson from Sweden <p>Lunch break, 13:00 – 14:00</p> <p>Workshop 1: 14:00 – 15:20</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using Future Visions to Build Policy Supporting Women-led Innovation <p>Coffee break 15:20 – 15:40</p> <p>Two parallel group sessions, 15:40 – 17:10</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop 2: Empowering Women to Lead: Shaping Policy for Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas. • Workshop 3: Policy Practice Discussions. <p>Feedback from the Workshops and Wrap Up 17:10 – 17:30</p> <p>Feedback from the FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board 17.30 - 17.45</p> <p>Networking Aperitif (*Only FLIARA innovation ambassadors) 18.00 - 19.00</p> <p>Networking Dinner 20.00</p>
Day 2 – Thursday January 30th 2025: Field visits – Women's Innovation Journeys
<p>Field visits and virtual tours 8 – 18</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting 3 women innovators in the Valle del Crati Area: • Rural innovator: Rosaria Amalia Capparelli, Mayor of San Benedetto Ullano and the operators of the SAI Project "Insieme a San Benedetto Ullano"; • Farming innovator: Nella De Vita - La Tatina Azienda Agricola;

- Farming innovator: Rita Bilotti- Serragiumenta - Discussion with the operators of LAG Valle del Crati.
- Virtual tour of women innovators in the south-east coast (Calabria) and discussion with Sofia De Matteis and other women innovators from the “We’re South” association.
- Virtual tour of women innovators in the Cilento Area (Campania) and discussion with Sarah Khoudja and other women innovators from the Circe association.

WORKSHOP DESCRIPTIONS

Guided by the GA the SAP outlines that one of the two main purposes of The FLIARA CoP is to develop an interchange platform for multi-actor exchanges, via a series of four EU workshops with all relevant key stakeholders. The SAP outlines how Workshops are a key part of the FLIARA conceptual framework to explore policy benchmarking, participatory scenario development for policy and broader policy dialogues. This will allow the exploration of the hypothesis and leverage point “Transforming policy and governance towards gender equality” and how “Governance solutions can provide opportunities, incentives, and support for female innovators”. In addition, by FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors and other women leading innovations in agriculture and rural areas being at the centre of the FLIARA CoP Network this also links to leverage point “Women in Decision-Making” and supports “Increasing women’s opportunities to participate in decisions concerning their lives”.

Continuing on from the Slovenian CoP event, three workshops were included in the Italian event, that feed into three different tasks in two different work packages. These tasks build on and feed into wider work packages, as outlined in the GA:

Table 12 Italy CoP Workshops Description as per GA

Work package WP4 – FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Workshop 2 - Task 4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design
The objectives of this activity are twofold: (a) verify the data already collected within the project in relation to public policies and laws which frame rural women’s innovations, and (b) to create a supportive community for women innovators to connect, share experiences, and foster collaboration with various types of stakeholders including policy/decision-makers, Local actions group/LEADER and researchers.
Work package WP5 – Policy Design and Assessment
Workshop 1 - Task 5.3: Develop new policy proposals
This workshop involves participants discussing future visions for farming and rural areas. The focus is on visions women could make an important contribution to and what policy is needed to make these a reality. Visions are picked from a range of options, such as local food, renewable energy, sustainable lifestyles.
Workshop 3 - Task 5.2: Policy practice discussions
This workshop aims to identify gaps in current policies and propose policy changes for female-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. Participants will share their experiences, insights, and opinions on policy issues from local to European levels.

Following the steps outlined in the SAP, each of the workshop leads added objectives for the workshop in the “FLIARA CoP task content builder” and in the lead up to the

event, they collaborated with the host to divide up the list of participants according to the already established principles of diversity, aiming to connect ambassadors, policy makers and others stakeholders, include language needs, and also taking into account prior participation in the same workshops during previous events. The structure was maintained similar to the two previous events, with Workshop 1/Task 5.3 happening on its own, and tasks T4.3 (Workshop 2) & T5.2 (Workshop 3) happen simultaneously in two different rooms. Workshop leads defined themes and needs (how many tables, what group size, what extra resources needed), with the following descriptions being shared in the Linktree, to describe the workshops in a more appealing way.

Table 13 Italy CoP Workshops Description

Work package WP4 – FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Workshop 2 - Task 4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design
This session builds on the insights gained from previous CoP events by further refining policy recommendations based on the findings of Task 4.3, which identified 11 key areas for policy improvement. Drawing from the data collected in WP1, WP3, and WP4 (D4.3), this workshop serves as a platform for women innovators to directly engage with policymakers and other stakeholders, ensuring their perspectives shape future policy design. Through structured discussions and participatory methods, the session fosters collaboration, consensus-building, and multi-actor engagement, which are crucial for WP5’s policy recommendation development. Key topics include entrepreneurship, access to finance, rural infrastructure, gender norms, digital skills, and education. The outcomes of this session will be documented, analysed, and integrated into WP5 deliverables to inform future policy frameworks that better support women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas.
Work package WP5 – Policy Design and Assessment
Workshop 1 - Task 5.3: Develop new policy proposals
This session builds on previous CoP events by continuing the vision group exercises, which have been used to gather policy suggestions addressing sustainability challenges. It consists of two parts: vision groups, where participants discuss policy solutions based on selected vision cards, and elaboration groups, which further develop these ideas by mapping a path from the envisioned future to the present using scenario cards. Rooted in WP2 findings, this task ensures that sustainability issues identified in previous research are directly addressed. Women entrepreneurs bring firsthand experience, making their input crucial in shaping policies that impact their lives. Discussions will centre on sustainability challenges, with a focus on local food systems, sustainable lifestyles, and policymaking. To ensure effective collaboration, diverse groups will be formed, and facilitators will guide discussions, including language support for Italian participants. The results will be shared through a brief summary and potentially a consortium meeting for further discussion.
Workshop 3 - Task 5.2: Policy practice discussions
This workshop aims to identify gaps and ideas to strengthen current policies on female-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas based on lived experiences of female farmers and entrepreneurs. Mixed groups of participants (6-9 persons) share their experiences, insights, and opinions on the challenges they faced during their innovation journey with their workaround or solutions. The workshop was organised in four tables, each table starting the discussion from a different perspective (female, innovation, agriculture, and rural entrepreneur). The second step in this workshop was to translate these problems and solutions into changes to be made in policy issues from local to European levels.

FLIARA COP ROADMAP

The process of FLIARA CoP Roadmap was implemented as per the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1, p 31). ECOLISE initiated the CoP event preparation by contacting the host institution – UNICAL, and proceeding, together with all partners involved, to prepare and deliver the event. Once the date was set and the venue booked – as confirmed by the host – the remainder of the preparation activities were carried out.

An essential step in preparing the CoP event was putting together the list of potential participants, which gathered all suggestions from Consortium members regarding relevant stakeholders to be invited to participate in the event. The list also included the FLIARA Ambassadors scheduled to attend the event, the FLIARA Consortium member, Italian women innovators interviewed within WP3 and present in Italy during the event, LAG representatives, members of national women's and agriculture networks, other researchers, etc. Once the list was consolidated, using the email templates available the invitation processes was initiated: after an initial invitation email, two reminders were sent, as well as confirmation email and a final email prior to the event with all the relevant information for the participants. CE and ECOLISE implemented seamlessly this process, updating the host recurrently with the relevant information about participants.

The logistical details of the Ambassadors and SAB were handled by the host institution, with support from ECOLISE and Galway. As the Tasks leads for the Workshops filled in their Task Content Builder Templates, these were made available to the host for the relevant logistical preparations. CE published all relevant information (Agenda, Travel, Guide, Workshop Descriptions, etc.) on the FLIARA website under the title of the event.

With the event about to start, the hosts printed the attendance sheets provided by CE, the booklets in Italian and in English containing information about all 20 Innovative Italian Women interviewed by FLIARA, as well as the factsheets of the 20 FLIARA ambassadors (in poster format) which were displayed during the event.

During both days, feedback survey forms were distributed in digital form to all participants in order to gather their feedback for the event. The Ethics Guardian has been monitoring the wellbeing of the Ambassadors present throughout the event. And the task leads provided their Tasks Reflection Template at the end of the event offering additional feedback on the implementation of their tasks.

FEEDBACK FROM THE ITALIAN COP

The FLIARA CoP event in Italy integrated monitoring, evaluation, and reflection to ensure a dynamic, responsive, and impactful knowledge-sharing space. The process involved continuous monitoring of CoP implementation and Ambassador well-being. Evaluation was conducted through structured feedback from ambassadors, consortium partners, and stakeholders, ensuring evidence-based improvements. The event was assessed using the digital tools Mentimeter. The event reinforced FLIARA's commitment to societal impact by ensuring stakeholder voices were heard, ethical standards maintained, and research findings meaningfully integrated into policy and practice.

In total, the event counted with 73 registered participants, out of which 10 were FLIARA innovation Ambassadors, 12 were Italian innovative women, 31 consortium members, 2 FLIARA Stakeholder Advisory Board members, and 18 other stakeholders.

METHODOLOGY FOR GATHERING FEEDBACK

As per SAP (D4.1), all FLIARA CoP events have in built monitoring and reporting mechanisms. The Ethics Guardian is responsible for monitoring and reporting on the wellbeing of the Ambassadors throughout the implementation of the event. The participants contribute with direct feedback but also are requested to fill in a feedback survey for each event day (see Annex 2). All task leads implementing activities during the event (the three workshops primarily) also provide their reflective feedback on how the implementation of the tasks went.

Table 14 Italy CoP: Registered Stakeholders & Feedback for both days

Type	Number
Ambassadors	10
Innovators	12
Consortium Partners	31
SAB	2
Stakeholders	18
Total	78

The total number of respondents to the Mentimeter feedback surveys reached 10 Ambassadors and 29 other stakeholders for day 1, and 5 Ambassadors and 18 other stakeholders for day 2. The highest possible score on Metimeter is 5, with the lowest being 0 for each question.

Table 15 Italy CoP: Stakeholder responses, Days 1 & 2

Stakeholder type	Day 1		Day 2	
	Responses	Group %	Responses	Group %
Ambassadors	10	100%	5	50%
Consortium Member	14	48%	11	61%
Policy or Decision Maker	0	0	0	0
Researcher	8	27%	5	28%
LAG Representative	2	7%	1	5%
Other type of stakeholder	2	7%	0	0
Woman Innovator	3	10%	1	5%
Total	39	100%	23	100%

The feedback surveys were tailored to the Ambassadors in order to better understand how specific activities they are included in – like the Visibility Campaign – are impacting them.

FEEDBACK FORM RESULTS - MENTIMETER

The overall score for the event by averaging all 4 surveys (Day 1 for Ambassadors, and respectively for Stakeholders, and Day 2 for Ambassadors and Stakeholders) was 4.7, with the Ambassadors considering the 2nd Day (fieldtrip day) as impeccable (overall rating of 5 - excellent).

The participants rated overall the communication about the FLIARA event, accessibility and inclusivity of needs, the food and social program for both days very highly. The easiness of the logistic process (the travel and accommodation arrangements) for Day 1, as well overall program for the FLIARA fieldtrip showed some room for improvement (being rated at 4.3 each, out of 5). The networking dinner during Day 1, as well as the - virtual tours of women innovators in the south-east coast (Calabria) and discussion with Sofia De Matteis and other women innovators from the We're South association and the virtual tour of women innovators in the Cilento Area (Campania) and discussion with Sarah Khoudja and other women innovators from the Circe association were rated as the most useful activities from Day 2.

Networking with women engaged in sustainable rural initiatives and engaging with the FLIARA Consortium and researchers more generally were rated highest in likely having a positive impact on the stakeholders' practices in the future for the two days respectively.

The feedback added to the open-ended questions by the participants highlighted the FLIARA project's positive impact as an inspiring catalyst for women-led innovation. Participants valued the opportunity for knowledge exchange and networking, particularly appreciating the Ambassador Impact Journey and the diversity of perspectives. However, there were suggestions for improvements, including more focused workshops, better organization of field trips, and clearer communication on logistics. The need for ongoing publication of materials, broader gender perspectives (e.g., work-life balance), and easier access to virtual content was also mentioned. Overall, the event was considered well-organized, insightful, and inspiring.

FEEDBACK FROM AMBASSADORS

The feedback surveys filled in by the Ambassadors indicated an overall high satisfaction with the event implementation (a score of 4.6 for Day 1 and 5 for Day 2). The social program on Day 1 (including the Networking Aperitif and Networking Dinner) was rated at 4.8. On Day 2, the overall program and FLIARA COP Field trip agenda and the social program were rated as excellent (5). Participating in the Ambassadors Journey activities was rated as most useful to participate in (4.8) during Day 1, with three of the four fieldtrip visits being also rated as very useful to participate in during Day 2.

Getting to know the other FLIARA Ambassadors was rated both days with the highest likely positive impact on the Ambassadors' innovative practice in the future, together with visiting and viewing projects of Italian FLIARA Ambassadors and innovators during Day 2. The event was highly appreciated for its organization and usefulness, with participants expressing a desire for more details on lunch, bathrooms, and breaks during the field trip. Overall, Day 2 was inspiring, showcasing valuable best practices.

According to the quotes added to the feedback survey by the FLIARA Ambassadors, the FLIARA CoP event in Rende, Italy, provided invaluable networking opportunities, fostering deep connections among powerful women entrepreneurs and stakeholders. The Ambassadors appreciated the chance to engage in meaningful discussions, exchange challenges, and offer mutual support, particularly in shaping policy and legal changes beneficial to women. While translation support for Italian participants would have enhanced inclusivity, the workshops successfully created a space to reflect on both the strengths and challenges of different experiences. Many expressed interest in seeing the long-term impact of FLIARA and how its outcomes would be implemented. The event reinforced the strength of the network, with participants eager to continue supporting one another in their businesses and future collaborations.

FEEDBACK FROM THE ETHICS GUARDIAN

According to the report from the Ethics Guardian, the implementation of the tasks at the FLIARA CoP event in Rende, Italy, was carried out effectively, ensuring high levels of engagement and participation. Ambassadors played a central role throughout the event, with dedicated time for their introductions, networking, and contributions during workshops and discussions. The workshops focused on policy support for women-led innovation, empowering women in agriculture and rural areas, and policy practice discussions, all of which saw active participation and knowledge exchange. A full-day field trip further enriched the experience, allowing rural innovators to showcase their work and engage in meaningful discussions. Ambassadors expressed enthusiasm and comfort in the collaborative environment, highlighting the welcoming atmosphere and valuable connections made. Monitoring and evaluation were successfully integrated, with feedback forms completed at the end of each day, ensuring continuous reflection and improvement. Overall, the event was well-organized, inclusive, and aligned with ethical guidelines, fostering a strong sense of community and collaboration among participants.

TASK REFLECTIONS

T5.3 - Workshop 1 / Develop new policy proposals

The implementation of this task during the FLIARA CoP event in Rende, Italy, effectively facilitated dynamic discussions through Vision and Elaboration groups, ensuring meaningful engagement among women innovators and other stakeholders. The vision groups successfully utilized vision cards to spark discussions on women's contributions to key sustainability areas, while the elaboration groups built on previous CoP findings, exploring policy pathways through scenario cards focused on Local Food, Policy Making, and Sustainable Lifestyles. Despite minor logistical challenges with space arrangements, the workshop structure functioned well, allowing for inclusive and productive exchanges. The presence of first-time vision group participants alongside experienced CoP members ensured diverse perspectives, enriching the discussions. Looking ahead, the next CoP event in Sweden is expected to maintain this dual-group structure for a final

round of data collection before progressing to scenario development and testing. However, further reflection on potential adaptations to enhance the final session will be conducted following a complete analysis of results.

T4.3 – Workshop 2 / Policy Design

The implementation of T4.3 at the FLIARA CoP event in Rende, Italy, successfully facilitated direct exchanges on policy topics among diverse stakeholders, including women innovators, FLIARA Ambassadors, Consortium Members, Researchers and LAG representatives. Participants engaged in policy design discussions, prioritizing key policy improvement areas identified in D4.3 and co-creating policy wishes and implementation strategies. The workshop design, developed in collaboration with Galway University and TU Delft, will inform WP5's final benchmarking report. The session space and operational setup were well-suited, and the presence of relevant stakeholders enriched discussions. Lessons learned suggest potential refinements for the next iteration in Sweden, including expanding the policy prioritization survey to a broader audience and integrating the presentation of T4.3 findings into the main CoP agenda. Additionally, organizers will consider streamlining the workshop's dynamic elements while maintaining its depth of insights, incorporating feedback from facilitators and CoP evaluations to enhance future sessions.

T5.2 – Workshop 3 / Policy Practice workshop

During this third version of the Policy Practice workshop, the semi structured approach based on the four main topics of the FLIARA project was used again. The general explanation at the beginning of the workshop to all participants was elaborated. Because some facilitators were the same during this workshop, the outcomes became more elaborated and explicit, which gave more insights in the innovation journey of the innovators and Ambassadors.

VISIBILITY CAMPAIGN

WP6 spearheaded the development of a comprehensive marketing campaign, designed to engage stakeholders as outlined in Deliverable 4.1. This initiative encompassed the creation of compelling visual assets, the coding of HTML emails, and the meticulous layout of promotional materials. The WP4 leader and the University of Calabria (UNICAL) played a crucial role in refining the content of these materials, ensuring accuracy and impact. The finalised promotional package, delivered to UNICAL, included ID tagnames, customisable PowerPoint templates for the event, Ambassador Journey templates, and a bilingual (Italian and English) booklet of female innovators. These booklets are accessible at: <https://fliara.eu/fliara-italy-cop/>. Crucially, all promotional materials featured images of the FLIARA Ambassadors, enhancing their visibility and recognition.

Furthermore, to showcase the contributions of the 20 female innovators representing each partner country, posters featuring their fact sheets were prominently displayed within the venue hall. These posters were strategically located across the hall to ensure

maximum visibility. These materials, printed by the event host, served as a visual testament to the project's impact. The vibrant and informative posters created a compelling visual narrative of the ambassadors' achievements.

The FLIARA CoP in Italy also provided a dedicated space for filming video interviews with three ambassadors. In alignment with Deliverable 6.2, FLIARA Ambassadors' buddies facilitated these recordings, with the WP6 leader directing the filming process. These videos captured the ambassadors' perspectives and experiences, offering valuable insights into their innovative work. In summary, the FLIARA CoP successfully highlighted the groundbreaking work of the FLIARA Ambassadors to stakeholders across the Mediterranean macro-region. The event generated significant traction on social media and the FLIARA website, demonstrating its effectiveness in raising awareness and fostering engagement. A detailed report by CE, available at [<https://fliara.eu/fliaras-3rd-community-of-practice-in-italy-showcases-female-led-innovation-in-rural-europe/>], further elaborates on the event's positive outcomes and the collaborative efforts of all partners.

LESSONS LEARNED AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The third FLIARA Community of Practice event in Rende confirmed the value of place-based learning, peer exchange and informal interaction within the CoP sequence. Feedback from Ambassadors and other participants highlighted strong satisfaction with the overall agenda and social programme, particularly in relation to networking and field-based activities. At the same time, monitoring data and qualitative feedback identified specific areas where design, facilitation and accessibility could be further strengthened, feeding directly into adaptations for the subsequent CoP in Sweden.

KEY STRENGTHS:

Dedicated Ambassador Networking and Co-Creation

In direct response to feedback from previous CoP events, the host partners introduced a dedicated networking aperitif exclusively for FLIARA Ambassadors. This moment was co-designed and co-organised together with the Italian Ambassadors, reflecting a clear shift toward shared ownership of the CoP process. The setting created a protected space for informal exchange, trust-building and peer support, strengthening relational ties among Ambassadors and reinforcing their role as active co-shapers of the Community of Practice.

Field Visit and Place-Based Learning

The Day 2 field visit was consistently identified as the most valuable element of the Rende CoP, particularly by the Ambassadors. Visiting the projects of Italian Ambassadors and women innovators enabled participants to engage directly with local practices, contextual challenges and solutions, reinforcing the importance of grounding policy and innovation discussions in lived rural realities. Food prepared by local actors further contributed to a welcoming and community-oriented atmosphere.

Peer Exchange and Networking

For Ambassadors, the opportunity to deepen relationships with other women innovators across Europe was among the most impactful aspects of Day 1. For other stakeholders, networking with women engaged in sustainable rural initiatives was likewise identified as a key benefit. These interactions strengthened transnational peer connections and supported the consolidation of the CoP as a relational space.

Agenda Design and Social Programme

The overall structure of the event, including its social elements, was positively received. Informal moments alongside structured activities supported relationship-building and trust, complementing the more formal workshop formats.

AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

Policy Workshops and Focus

Feedback indicated mixed perceptions of the policy workshop sessions on Day 1. The newly introduced format of the T4.3 policy design workshop (“Empowering Women to Lead”) received lower usefulness ratings compared to other activities. Qualitative comments suggested that clearer thematic focus, stronger facilitation and attention to group dynamics would improve outcomes. This feedback will inform subsequent refinements of the workshop design for the Våxjö CoP.

Language Accessibility

Stakeholders highlighted the need for stronger language accessibility, particularly Italian translation during workshops and field visits. While an Italian-speaking table was organised for some sessions, audio volume during the field visits reduced accessibility for some participants.

Visibility Campaign Integration (WP6)

Participation in the Visibility Campaign was perceived by some Ambassadors as less useful compared to other CoP activities. This feedback indicated the need for clearer framing of visibility work, improved scheduling and better integration with the overall CoP agenda, an issue addressed in later events.

Logistics and Communication

The cancellation of one field visit stop due to unforeseen circumstances affected participant experience, underlining the importance of clear and timely communication when agenda changes occur. Additional suggestions included providing clearer information on field-trip logistics, planned breaks and accessibility of facilities.

REFLECTIONS FOR THE LAST COP

The Rende CoP highlighted both the strengths and challenges of combining dense workshop agendas with field-based learning and networking. Monitoring and feedback mechanisms proved essential in identifying where adjustments were needed, particularly in relation to workshop focus, facilitation and accessibility. These insights will directly inform the design and delivery of the fourth CoP in Växjö, contributing to the iterative refinement of the FLIARA Community of Practice in line with the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1).

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS REGARDING THE EVENT

FLIARA event report

- FLIARA's 3th Community of Practice in Italy Showcases Female-Led Innovation in Rural Europe: <https://fliara.eu/events/join-our-third-community-of-practice-networking-event-in-italy/>
- Event report on the FLIARA website (CE): <https://fliara.eu/fliaras-3rd-community-of-practice-in-italy-showcases-female-led-innovation-in-rural-europe/>
- Article on UNICAL website: <https://www.unical.it/contents/calendars/view/eventi-unical/2969/>

ANNEX 4 – EVENT REPORT: 4TH FLIARA COP NETWORKING EVENT – VÄXJÖ, SWEDEN, 15–16 MAY 2025

This report presents the results and reflections from the fourth and final FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) networking event, held in Växjö, Sweden, on May 14-15, 2025. As outlined in the Strategic Action Plan (SAP), the CoP events are designed to foster exchange, co-creation, and empowerment among women innovators in rural and agricultural contexts across Europe. These reports contribute to Deliverable D4.2, which consolidates the outcomes of all four CoP events.

In Växjö, the FLIARA team prioritized inclusion, visibility, and collaborative learning, with an emphasis on Swedish experiences in policy, gender roles, and cross-sectoral rural innovation. The Ethics Guardian monitored the wellbeing and engagement of the Ambassadors throughout the event. Feedback gathered via digital tools, interviews, and reflections by task leaders is incorporated into this report.

Figure 36 Sweden CoP participants during the field trip (day 1, 14th of May 25).

COP EVENT 4: VÄXJÖ, SWEDEN, MAY 14-15, 2025

The fourth CoP event took place at Linnaeus University in Växjö. Day 1 focused on project presentations, a workshop on envisioning policy futures, and the Ambassador Innovation Journeys. In the afternoon and evening, participants visited Ödevata Gårdshotell, a sustainable tourism site led by a FLIARA Ambassador. Day 2 included additional project results, parallel workshops, policy discussions, and a final celebration of the achievements of the CoPs.

The event brought together Ambassadors, researchers, policymakers and European Commission representatives, including a keynote intervention by Commissioner Jessika Roswall (Environment, Water Resilience and a Competitive Circular Economy). A total of 61 participants attended the event, including 10 FLIARA Ambassadors, consortium partners (29), researchers, Swedish women innovators (8), policymakers (6), and LAG representatives (3), as well as activists and media representatives.

DESCRIPTION OF SWEDISH COP ACTIVITIES

The 4th Community of Practice (CoP) of the FLIARA project, held in Växjö, Sweden, brought together over 60 participants in a dynamic setting that amplified women's voices in rural innovation. The event marked a critical space for cross-sectoral dialogue among

women innovators, policymakers, researchers, and civil society actors. Presentations from FLIARA researchers identified significant gaps in gender-responsive measures within CAP strategic plans, underlining the urgent need for equitable access to finance, land, training, and inclusion in innovation ecosystems. These insights directly shaped policy benchmarking activities and advanced concrete proposals for structural change.

Seven FLIARA Ambassadors shared their sustainable innovation journeys across eco-tourism, education, social farming, and rural enterprise, using their experiences to critique systemic barriers such as underinvestment, gaps in infrastructure, and persistent gendered norms, as well as they identified transferable solutions and opportunities. Their participation was a clear political act—asserting visibility, influence, and agency in a space where women’s leadership is often sidelined. Through workshops on benchmarking, policy design, and futures thinking, participants collectively articulated bottom-up, network-based approaches to rural transformation, rooted in contextual knowledge and local realities.

Cross-sector collaboration was a recurring theme, with frameworks such as the “five Cs” (competence, contact, capital, continuity, context) helping structure action across public, private, and civil domains. Comparative reflections on Sweden’s gender policies—particularly in childcare and parental leave—demonstrated how institutional frameworks can actively shift societal expectations and redistribute care and labour. Cultural elements, such as a performance by Finnish Ambassador Sonja Jokiranta, were strategically positioned to foreground the role of creative expression in political storytelling and community mobilisation. The Växjö CoP consolidated FLIARA’s participatory policy approach, engaging over 350 people across four CoPs and laying the foundation for the project’s final policy outputs and conference in Brussels.

Table 16 Swedish CoP Agenda

FLIARA CoP Networking Event	
Day 0 – Tuesday May 13 2025	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tuesday, 13 May (Pre-conference – Voluntary Activities) • 17:30 – 19:00 Guided tour at The House of Emigrants (Utvandrarnas hus) • 19:00 Dinner at Kafé deluxe (at your own expense) 	
Day 1 – Wednesday May 14 2025	
Venue: Växjö Campus – House K	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8:30 – 9:00 Registration and Poster Exhibition at Campus: Glas Gallery • 9:00 – 10:00 Launch of the FLIARA CoP • Kerstin Årmann and Annie Roos – Linnaeus University • Maura Farrell – University of Galway • 10:00 – 10:30 Results from FLIARA Project • Harnessing the FLIARA Framework: Ideas for Future Policy to Boost Women-led Rural and Farm Innovation • Empowering Women for Rural Sustainability: Insights from FLIARA’s Foresight and Trend Analysis 	

- Lessons from FLIARA Case Studies on Women-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
- 10:30 – 12:00 | **Cross-sector Collaboration for Rural Development – Opportunities and Challenges**
- Prof. Malin Tillmar – Linnaeus University
- 12:00 – 13:15 | **Fika at Campus: Glas Gallery**
- *Ambassador Exclusive Fika (only for FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors) at Campus: BusinessLab*
- 13:15 – 14:45 | **Workshop 1:**
- Using Future Visions to Build Policy Supporting Women-led Innovation
- 14:45 – 21:00 | **Field Trip**
- Bus ride to Ödevata (departure from campus)
- Bus ride back to Växjö (drop-off in the city and at campus)

Day 2 – Thursday May 15 2025

Venue: Växjö Campus – House K

- 8:30 – 9:00 | Registration and Poster Exhibition at Campus: Glas Gallery
- 9:00 – 10:00 | **Welcome Speech**
- Peter Aronsson – Vice-Chancellor, Linnaeus University
- 10:00 – 10:30 | **Results from FLIARA Project**
- Benchmarking? Counting What Counts to Better Support Women-led Rural and Farm Innovation
- Bringing Practice into Policy
- 10:30 – 12:15 | Talks and Discussions
- Keynote: **Jessika Roswall – Commissioner for Environment, Water Resilience and a Competitive Circular Economy**
- “Explaining The Latte Dad”: Prof. Helene Ahl – Jönköping University
- Panel: Policy Changes to Support More Women-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
- 12:15 – 13:15 | Lunch
- 13:15 – 13:45 | **Talk: The Feelgood Entrepreneur – From Crisis to Community in Small Towns and Villages**
- Piia Posti – Senior Lecturer, Linnaeus University
- 13:45 – 15:30 | **Parallel Workshops**
- Empowering Women to Lead: Shaping Policy for Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
- Policy Practice Discussions
- 15:30 – 16:00 | Fika
- 16:00 – 16:30 | Panel Discussion: Reflecting on the Workshops
- 16:30 – 17:00 | **Closing and Celebration**
- 17:15 – 18:00 | Closing Reception
- Evening | Voluntary Dinner

WORKSHOPS

Guided by the GA the SAP outlines that one of the two main purposes of The FLIARA CoP is to develop an interchange platform for multi-actor exchanges, via a series of four EU workshops with all relevant key stakeholders. The SAP outlines how Workshops are a key part of the FLIARA conceptual framework to “explore policy benchmarking, participatory scenario development for policy and broader policy dialogues. This will allow the exploration of the hypothesis and leverage point “Transforming policy and governance towards gender equality” and how “Governance solutions can provide

opportunities, incentives, and support for female innovators”. In addition, by FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors and other women leading innovations in agriculture and rural areas being at the centre of the FLIARA CoP Network this also links to leverage point “Women in Decision-Making” and supports “Increasing women’s opportunities to participate in decisions concerning their lives”.

Building on the Italian CoP event, three workshops were included in the Swedish event, that feed into three different tasks in two different work packages. These tasks build on and feed into wider work packages, as outlined in the GA:

Table 17 Swedish CoP Workshops Overview

Work package WP4 – FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Workshop 2 - Empowering Women to Lead (Task 4.3)
This workshop explored priority areas for policy benchmarking, using both surveys and collaborative “policy wish” creation. A mix of stakeholders participated in dynamic discussions. The feedback emphasized the role of context, as some Swedish tables found traditional gender norms less pressing compared to their peers from other regions.
Work package WP5 – Policy Design and Assessment
Workshop 1 - Using Future Visions to Build Policy Supporting Women-led Innovation (Task 5.3)
Led by UTU and Galway, this workshop employed vision cards to engage participants in discussions around policy-making and sustainability. Participants were enthusiastic and contributed to new scenario ideas. The standout vision theme in Sweden was sustainable farming, marking a shift from previous CoP events.
Workshop 3 - Policy Practice Discussions (Task 5.2)
This workshop aims to identify gaps and ideas to strengthen current policies on female-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas based on lived experiences of female farmers and entrepreneurs. Mixed groups of participants (6-9 persons) share their experiences, insights, and opinions on the challenges they faced during their innovation journey with their workaround or solutions. The workshop was organised in four tables, each table starting the discussion from a different perspective (female, innovation, agriculture, and rural entrepreneur). The second step in this workshop was to translate these problems and solutions into changes to be made in policy issues from local to European levels.

Following the steps outlined in the sap, each of the workshop leads added objectives for the workshop in the “FLIARA cop task content builder” and in the lead up to the event, they collaborated with the host to divide the list of participants according to the already established principles of diversity – aiming to connect ambassadors, policy makers and others stakeholders, include language needs, and also taking into account prior participation in the same workshops during previous events. The structure was maintained similar to the two previous events, with workshop 1/task 5.3 happening on its own, and workshop 2/tasks 4.3 & workshop 3/task 5.2 happened simultaneously in two different rooms. Workshop leads defined themes and needs (how many tables, group size, and extra resources needed).

FLIARA COP ROADMAP

Event planning followed the SAP and leveraged the experience of previous CoPs. ECOLISE, Consulta Europa and LNU collaborated on invitations, logistics, and

materials. Workshops were co-developed with Galway, TU Delft, and UTU. Materials, including posters, vision cards, and Ambassador fact sheets, were prepared in advance. During both days, feedback survey forms were distributed in digital form to all participants in order to gather their feedback for the event. The Ethics Guardian monitored the wellbeing of the Ambassadors present throughout the event. And the task leads provided their Tasks Reflection Template at the end of the event offering additional feedback on the implementation of their tasks.

FEEDBACK FROM THE SWEDISH COP

The FLIARA CoP event in Sweden integrated monitoring, evaluation, and reflection to ensure a dynamic, responsive, and impactful knowledge-sharing space. The process involved continuous monitoring of CoP implementation and ambassador well-being. Evaluation was conducted through structured feedback from Ambassadors, consortium partners, and stakeholders, ensuring evidence-based improvements. The event was assessed using the digital tool Mentimeter. The event reinforced FLIARA's commitment to societal impact by ensuring stakeholder voices were heard, ethical standards maintained, and research findings meaningfully integrated into policy and practice.

FEEDBACK FORM RESULTS - MENTIMETER

On the Stakeholder side, 20 responses were collected on Day 1 and 16 on Day 2, with participants including women innovators, public authority representatives, and other relevant rural and research actors. Stakeholders gave Day 1 an average score of 4.7 out of 5, highlighting the rich mix of participants, the practical learning from the field trip, and the integration of policy perspectives. On Day 2, Stakeholders also rated the event at 4.7, acknowledging the value of policy discussions, storytelling elements, and the collaborative environment. The celebration segment was well received here too, reinforcing the sense of closure and achievement after a series of in-depth CoP events. The highest scores (5.0) were given to the Ödevata field trip and Day 2's policy talks, notably Helene Ahl's session and the Ambassador panel. The lowest score (3.5) came from some Stakeholders on Day 1, who cited the long day and fatigue during the evening networking dinner as limiting full engagement, though even this rating remained within a positive spectrum.

FEEDBACK FROM AMBASSADORS

Feedback from the 4th FLIARA Community of Practice event reveals consistently high and very high levels of satisfaction among Ambassadors. On Day 1, 8 out of 10 participating Ambassadors responded to the feedback form, awarding an average score of 4.8 out of 5. They especially appreciated the field trip to Ödevata and the networking opportunities it offered, together with the exclusive Ambassador "fika" (coffee break). On Day 2, 6 Ambassadors responded, giving the event a perfect score of 5.0, reflecting their enthusiasm for the workshops and gender policy discussions, informative talks by experts regarding the situation in Sweden and specific gender equality policy approach,

and the collaborative spirit of the sessions. The celebration moment at the close of the event was also highly appreciated by Ambassadors, noted as a meaningful and joyful culmination to the two-day experience and the overall series of FLIARA CoP Events. The highest scores were consistently attributed to the immersive field visit and networking activities. There were no low scores recorded from Ambassadors, indicating satisfaction across all aspects.

FEEDBACK FROM THE ETHICS GUARDIAN

The Ethics Guardian's report confirms the quantitative feedback received via survey from the participating Ambassadors. The report highlights the Ambassadors' comfort, motivation, and enthusiastic participation in all sessions, from workshops and networking to field visits and the celebratory closing. The celebration moment was frequently mentioned in both formal and informal feedback as an uplifting and affirming conclusion. Ambassadors expressed a strong sense of belonging and appreciation for the space created, describing the event as energising, well-paced, and deeply valuable. Their interest in continuing involvement - despite potential personal cost - further underlines the impact of the series of four FLIARA CoP Networking Events. Together, the survey data and ethics reflections paint a coherent and compelling picture: the CoP in Sweden was a standout experience that empowered Ambassadors, strengthened their connections, and reinforced their central role in shaping women-led innovation in rural Europe.

TASK REFLECTIONS

T5.3 - Workshop 1 / Develop new policy proposals

The Vision Cards workshop in Växjö proved highly engaging and collaborative, with participants showing strong interest in discussing future scenarios for women-led innovation. Compared to earlier CoPs, results from Sweden stood out: "sustainable farming" emerged as the theme seen as offering the most opportunity for women to drive transformation—more prominently than in other countries. The activity, jointly planned by UTU and Galway, used cards co-developed by partners across all CoP sites. Participants worked in groups without designated note takers, encouraging active dialogue and shared initiative. The open format enabled rich exchange and co-creation, while the facilities supported a comfortable and well-resourced environment. The input from this session will be synthesized with results from all CoPs to generate final scenario outputs. Stakeholder representation was considered well-balanced, with strong Swedish participation adding valuable local perspective to the broader European insights.

T4.3 – Workshop 2 / Policy Design

The policy benchmarking workshop effectively engaged both Ambassadors and stakeholders in assessing key policy priorities and co-developing future policy wishes. Designed by ECOLISE in collaboration with Galway University and refined after the Italian CoP, the workshop included an assessment of existing policy priorities followed

by a policy wish-building exercise. Feedback indicated that participants appreciated the structured yet flexible format, which included time for solo reflection, idea recording with post-its, and open group discussions. Interestingly, the discussions revealed important contextual differences—while one group dismissed the relevance of addressing traditional gender norms in Scandinavia, others found the topic highly pertinent. This nuance highlights the value of context-sensitive approaches in policy development. The room setup, materials, and facilitation contributed to an effective environment for exchange. The outcomes of this session will feed directly into the Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3), helping to anchor policy recommendations in both European-level priorities and national realities.

T5.2 – Workshop 3 / Policy Practice workshop

The more effective layout of the Policy practice workshop format of Italy was executed during this fourth Community of Practice in Sweden again. The layout of the introduction, the oral presentation, the forms for notetaking and the summary were executed again and were effective. Because the organisation of the workshop was similar, the results became more effective and the notes more elaborated, due to the fact that the facilitators could ask for more information.

VISIBILITY CAMPAIGN

The structure of the event and planning of the organisers worked well thanks to the Strategic Action Plan developed under T4.1.

Linnaeus University, in collaboration with WP6 lead Consulta Europa, organized visual documentation, interviews, and poster exhibitions throughout the event. Ambassador videos were recorded in dedicated spaces. Materials from the event will contribute to the WP6 deliverables and enhance dissemination.

The museum visit, musical performance, and social events enriched storytelling for media outreach. The Swedish Community of Practice (CoP) event addressed WP6's need to record videos with FLIARA Ambassadors. LNU, the event organisers, structured the activities to provide an impactful experience for all participants.

LESSONS LEARNED AND FLIARA COP OUTCOME

The Swedish CoP represented the culmination of FLIARA's iterative learning across previous events, delivering the strongest results to date. With the highest overall scores from both Ambassadors and Stakeholders, the event confirmed the value of careful co-design, local contextualisation, and structured facilitation. Exclusive networking moments - such as the Ambassadors' fika sessions - proved essential in deepening relationships and enabling cross-national collaboration. Workshops were politically meaningful, with Ambassadors actively shaping discussions on gender-responsive policy, futures thinking, and benchmarking. The Ethics Report confirmed the welcoming environment and strong engagement throughout. This final CoP demonstrated the effectiveness of building transnational feminist learning spaces rooted in local realities.

A key lesson is that trust and connection, carefully nurtured by support network and learning opportunities are critical to sustaining co-creation. As we look ahead, there is real hope that the bond formed among Ambassadors will outlive the project itself, carrying forward the community of practice as a self-sustaining network for women-led rural innovation.

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE EVENT

- FLIARA's 4th Community of Practice in Sweden Showcases Female-Led Innovation in Rural Europe, including video recordings: <https://fliara.eu/events/join-our-fourth-community-of-practice-networking-event-in-sweden/>
- Event report on the FLIARA website (CE): <https://fliara.eu/fliara-project-successfully-concludes-4th-community-of-practice-in-vaxjo-sweden/>
- News article on LNU's website: <https://lnu.se/mot-linneuniversitetet/aktuellt/nyheter/2025/innovatorer-politiker-och-forskare-utforskade-kvinnliga-entreprenorers-roll-pa-landsbygden/>

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